

Pricing Prediction Markets: Risk Premiums, Incomplete Markets, and a Decomposition Framework

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Working Paper — March 2026

This version: April 3, 2026

Abstract

Prediction markets—binary contracts on real-world events—lack the pricing infrastructure available to every other major asset class. This paper proposes a three-layer decomposition framework that, to my knowledge, is the first to formally separate physical event probability from a pricing wedge in prediction markets. The framework combines a log-odds state variable, jump-diffusion dynamics in log-odds space, and a Wang (2000) probability distortion: $p^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda)$. Because prediction market contracts are structurally equivalent to binary options in *incomplete* markets (Manski, 2006; Harrison and Pliska, 1983), observed prices necessarily embed both event probability and a pricing wedge that no-arbitrage reasoning alone cannot separate. The Wang transform provides a single-parameter decomposition and generates the favorite-longshot bias as a direct mathematical consequence. Calibration on 2,460 resolved Polymarket contracts yields $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = 0.176$ ($p < 10^{-10}$), consistent with catastrophe bond markets. Cross-platform validation across $N = 291,309$ contracts from Polymarket, Kalshi, Metaculus, Good Judgment Open, INFER, and Manifold confirms a positive, significant λ on all real-money platforms (pooled $\hat{\lambda} = 0.183$), while the play-money platform Manifold exhibits $\hat{\lambda} < 0$, consistent with overconfidence absent financial stakes. A stacked panel model reveals that the pricing wedge is time-varying, decaying with a half-life of 33% of contract lifetime on the 12-day subsample, with slower decay on the full 28-day sample—linking the cross-sectional duration effect to within-contract information arrival.

JEL Classification: G13, G14, G12, D81

Keywords: prediction markets, Wang transform, incomplete markets, binary options, favorite-longshot bias, pricing wedge, distortion risk measures, Polymarket, Kalshi

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1 Introduction

1.1 A Market Without a Model

Prediction markets have crossed the threshold from academic curiosity to consequential financial markets. Polymarket processed over \$3.5 billion in notional volume during the 2024 U.S. presidential election cycle. Kalshi, a CFTC-regulated prediction market exchange, won a landmark federal court ruling in 2024 that legitimized event contracts as financial instruments. ICE invested \$2 billion in Polymarket at an \$8 billion pre-money valuation in 2025.² In early 2026, Cboe announced plans to launch prediction market contracts packaged as vertical option spreads.³

Despite this institutional validation, prediction markets lack the theoretical infrastructure that underpins every other major asset class. Equity options have Black-Scholes (1973) and its descendants. Credit markets have Merton’s structural model and reduced-form intensity frameworks. Fixed income has Vasicek, CIR, and HJM. Prediction markets lack a widely accepted pricing framework. Prices are formed by order flow on CLOBs or by automated market makers (Hanson, 2007), but no theory connects these prices to a stochastic process, no implied volatility surface exists, and no formal framework addresses relative value or risk aggregation.

The absence of a pricing paradigm is not merely an aesthetic concern. It has concrete consequences:

1. **No probability decomposition.** Are prediction market prices probabilities? Manski (2006) showed, in a formal model of heterogeneous beliefs, that they are not in general: observed prices embed both beliefs *and* risk preferences, and the equilibrium price need not equal the mean belief. But without a model, there is no way to separate the two.
2. **No relative value.** Contracts on different events cannot be compared on a risk-adjusted basis. Is a Greenland acquisition contract at $p = 0.10$ cheap relative to a Fed rate cut contract at $p = 0.05$? No metric exists.
3. **No risk management.** Portfolio risk across multiple event contracts cannot be aggregated without a model of co-movement.
4. **No explanation of systematic biases.** The favorite-longshot bias (FLB)—documented across 300,000+ Kalshi contracts by Bürgi, Deng, and Whelan (2025)—shows that low-probability events are systematically overpriced, but no structural pricing model explains *why*.

²Source: ICE Press Release via BusinessWire, October 7, 2025.

³Source: Cboe press release, February 2026.

1.2 What Practitioners Currently Use

The absence of a paradigm does not mean the absence of trading. Susquehanna (SIG) became Kalshi’s first institutional market maker in 2024; Jump Trading reportedly negotiated small equity stakes in both platforms in exchange for liquidity provision, though finalization was not independently confirmed at the time of writing.⁴ Over 30% of Polymarket wallets now employ AI-based trading agents, according to an estimate reported by the on-chain analytics platform LayerHub; the underlying methodology has not, to my knowledge, been independently validated.⁵

What these firms use is an *ad hoc* assembly of tools from adjacent domains:

- **Fair value:** The Black-Scholes cash-or-nothing formula $F = e^{-r\tau}\Phi(d_2)$, applied directly to event contracts. The critical input is σ —but there is no established method for calibrating it. Each firm uses proprietary models.
- **Quote management:** Avellaneda-Stoikov (2008) optimal market making, with spreads scaled by binary option greeks. No formal adaptation to the bounded probability domain has been published.
- **Position sizing:** Kelly criterion for binary payoffs, $f^* = (bp - q)/b$, typically run at 25–50% fractional Kelly.

The critical gap is that prediction markets lack a standardized, continuously updated fair-value signal—the kind of pricing infrastructure that every other major asset class takes for granted. This paper proposes a framework that fills this gap.

1.3 Contributions

This paper proposes an integrated pricing and decomposition framework for prediction markets and validates it empirically across 291,309 contracts from eight data sources spanning six platforms and eleven years.

Framework architecture. The pricing model has three layers. *Layer 1:* a log-odds state variable that maps bounded prices to \mathbb{R} , yielding a natural domain for stochastic modeling (Section 3.2). *Layer 2:* a jump-diffusion dynamics specification in log-odds space, following Dalen (2025), under which the pricing formula reduces to the Black-Scholes binary option formula (Section 3.2). *Layer 3:* the Wang (2000) probability distortion operator—originally developed for catastrophe bond pricing—decomposes observed prices into physical probability and a pricing wedge: $p^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda)$. No prior work has applied the Wang transform to prediction markets. The decomposition operationalizes the Manski (2006) critique by providing

⁴Source: Bloomberg, February 2026.

⁵Source: LayerHub via CoinDesk, March 2026.

a specific, estimable functional form for the distortion that separates event probability from the pricing wedge parameter λ (Section 3).

1. *FLB as a structural consequence.* $\lambda > 0$ generates the favorite-longshot bias as a direct mathematical consequence: longshots are proportionally more overpriced than favorites (Section 3.3). Contract-level calibration against 2,460 resolved Polymarket contracts yields $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = 0.176$ ($p < 10^{-10}$) (Section 5).
2. *Cross-platform spread interpretation.* The framework interprets Polymarket–Kalshi price differences as reflecting different pricing wedge loadings ($\lambda_K \neq \lambda_P$), providing structural content to the price discovery finding independently documented by Ng et al. (2026) (Section 5.5).
3. *Cross-platform and temporal validation.* I validate the framework on $N = 291,309$ contracts from eight data sources across six platforms (Polymarket, Kalshi, Metaculus, Good Judgment Open, INFER, Manifold) spanning 2015–2026, confirming that $\lambda > 0$ is a robust feature of real-money prediction markets. The play-money platform Manifold exhibits $\lambda < 0$ (overconfidence), providing a natural control. Kalshi year-by-year estimates demonstrate temporal stability of $\lambda \in [0.14, 0.29]$ over 2022–2026 (Section 6).
4. *Log-odds stylized facts.* Building on the log-odds state variable used concurrently by Dalen (2025), I document that log-odds levels of prediction market contracts exhibit the same stylized facts as equity log-prices—random-walk behavior (unit root in x_t), fat tails (kurtosis 6–12 in increments), and volatility clustering—supporting a diffusion-based modeling approach (Section 4).
5. *Incompleteness formalization.* Drawing on the Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (Harrison and Pliska, 1983) and the Manski (2006) critique, I formalize the observation that prediction market contracts are structurally equivalent to cash-or-nothing binary options operating in incomplete markets, where the risk-neutral measure is non-unique and prices embed both probability and a pricing wedge (Section 3). This motivates the need for the decomposition framework.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 positions this work within the relevant literatures. Section 3 develops the theoretical framework: the incompleteness of prediction markets, the log-odds state variable, the Wang transform decomposition, and assembles the complete pricing model (Section 3.5). Section 4 describes the data and documents stylized facts supporting the log-odds framework. Section 5 presents the empirical results, including robustness checks and Monte Carlo validation (Section 5.6). Section 6 validates the framework across eight data sources spanning six platforms and $N = 291,309$ contracts (2015–2026). Section 7 discusses extensions. Section 8 concludes.

2 Related Literature

This paper sits at the intersection of four literatures: stochastic modeling of prediction markets, the interpretation of prediction market prices, the favorite-longshot bias, and applications of the Wang transform.

Stochastic modeling. Dalen (2025) proposes a logit jump-diffusion in risk-neutral (\mathbb{Q}) space with a martingale drift constraint, calibration pipeline, and belief-volatility surface. Dalen’s contribution and mine are complementary and address different problems. Dalen works entirely within the risk-neutral measure, taking \mathbb{Q} as given and building a market-making kernel; this paper asks *which* \mathbb{Q} the market selects and *how* it relates to the physical measure P . The Wang transform provides the P -to- \mathbb{Q} bridge. In principle, one could use Dalen’s logit jump-diffusion for the dynamics and the Wang transform for the measure change, combining both frameworks. Earlier, Archak and Ipeiritis (2009) modeled InTrade prices using Itô diffusions for latent ability processes, deriving contract price volatility as a function of current price and time to expiry.

Probability interpretation. Manski (2006) showed that interpreting prediction market prices directly as probabilities lacks formal justification: equilibrium price reflects a quantile of the belief distribution and only partially identifies the mean belief. Wolfers and Zitzewitz (2006) showed prices approximate mean beliefs under log utility and that broader model classes often yield similar results; Gjerstad (2004) proved the sufficiency of the log-utility condition. This paper operationalizes the Manski critique by providing a specific functional form for the distortion.

Favorite-longshot bias. The FLB has been documented in horse racing (Griffith, 1949; Snowberg and Wolfers, 2010), sports betting (Whelan, 2024), and prediction markets (Bürigi, Deng, and Whelan, 2025). Explanations include risk-loving preferences (Ali, 1977), probability weighting (Barberis and Huang, 2008), adverse selection (Shin, 1991, 1993), and noise (Ottaviani and Sorensen, 2010). Jullien and Salanié (2000) estimated expected utility, rank-dependent, and cumulative prospect theory models on racetrack data, finding that inverse-S shaped probability weighting—overweighting of small probabilities and underweighting of large ones—was a key driver of FLB, with cumulative prospect theory providing the best fit. The Wang transform provides a parametric complement to these nonparametric estimates. The Wang transform provides a unifying structural mechanism that nests the risk-averse market maker explanation (Whelan, 2024).

Wang transform applications. Wang (2000, 2004) applied the transform to catastrophe bond pricing ($\hat{\lambda} \approx 0.45$) and proposed it as a universal pricing framework for financial and insurance risks. Kijima and Muromachi (2008) derived the transform from Bühlmann’s economic premium principle, establishing an equilibrium foundation. Hamada and Sherris (2003) showed it recovers the Black-Scholes formula in the lognormal case and related the distortion parameter to systematic risk. Pelsser (2008) showed that the Wang transform is not consistent with arbitrage-free pricing for general stochastic processes, implying it is not a universal pricing framework; the present application to incomplete markets sidesteps this critique. Huang,

Sun, and Zhang (2024) recently generalized the transform to flexible probability weighting functions for lottery-like equities, embedding it within the Pi-CAPM framework. The present paper appears to be the first to apply the Wang transform to prediction markets or to derive the favorite-longshot bias as a consequence of the transform.

Prediction market design and calibration. Wolfers and Zitzewitz (2004) provide the standard survey on prediction market contract design and information aggregation. Servan-Schreiber, Wolfers, Pennock, and Galebach (2004) compare real-money and play-money prediction markets, finding similar forecasting accuracy—a result relevant to the interpretation of the Manifold play-money control in Section 6. Le (2026) argues that prediction market calibration is structured by horizon, domain, and trade size, complementing the heterogeneity analysis in Sections 5.3 and 5.6. Ostrovsky (2012) proves that in dynamic trading with separable securities, prices converge to the pooled-information posterior—a result relevant to the time-varying λ decay documented in Section 5.4. Gneiting, Balabdaoui, and Raftery (2007) provide the foundational treatment of probabilistic calibration, against which the Wang transform can be understood as a parametric recalibration map.

Bayesian approaches. Madrigal-Cianci, Monsalve Maya, and Breakey (2026) recast prediction markets as Bayesian inverse problems in log-odds space, providing posterior uncertainty quantification on probability estimates.

3 Theoretical Framework

3.1 Prediction Markets as Incomplete-Market Binary Options

A prediction market contract pays \$1 if event E occurs at or before time T , and \$0 otherwise. This is the payoff of a cash-or-nothing binary option (Rubinstein and Reiner, 1991):

$$\text{Payoff} = \$1 \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\{E \text{ occurs}\}}$$

In standard options theory, the Black-Scholes price of a cash-or-nothing binary call is:

$$C_{\text{binary}} = e^{-rT} \Phi(d_2), \quad d_2 = \frac{\ln(S/K) + (r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}$$

The contract price p_t is the risk-neutral probability of the event:

$$p_t = e^{-rt} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[\mathbf{1}_{\{E\}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t]$$

For the short maturities typical of prediction markets (days to months), $e^{-rt} \approx 1$, so $p_t \approx$

$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[\mathbf{1}_E \mid \mathcal{F}_t]$. The structural equivalence tells us *what* to price. But standard tools cannot tell us *how*, because the market is incomplete.

Terminology. Throughout this paper, I use the following terms consistently. The *physical probability* p^* denotes the objective likelihood of event E under the data-generating measure P . The *market price* p^{mkt} denotes the observed contract price. The *risk-adjusted probability* $\hat{p}^* = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^{\text{mkt}}) - \hat{\lambda})$ denotes the estimated physical probability after stripping the pricing wedge. I avoid the terms **true probability**, ‘‘fair value,’’ and ‘‘actuarially fair value’’ except where context requires them, as they can conflate distinct concepts.

Proposition 1 (Incompleteness). *Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}, P)$ be a filtered probability space supporting a prediction market contract C on event E . If E is not perfectly correlated with any traded asset, then:*

1. *No self-financing portfolio replicates the payoff $\mathbf{1}_E$.*
2. *The set of equivalent martingale measures \mathcal{Q} contains more than one element.*
3. *The no-arbitrage price lies in an interval $[\underline{p}, \bar{p}]$ with $\underline{p} < \bar{p}$.*

Proof sketch. The event E introduces a risk factor that is not fully spanned by—i.e., not attainable as a linear combination of payoffs from—existing traded assets. By the Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (Harrison and Pliska, 1981, 1983), market completeness requires $|\mathcal{Q}| = 1$, which fails whenever the payoff $\mathbf{1}_E$ is not attainable—i.e., lies outside the marketed subspace generated by admissible self-financing strategies. Even when E is partially correlated with traded assets (e.g., Fed rate decisions that affect bond prices), there generically remains residual event-specific risk that cannot be hedged, ensuring incompleteness. The bounds \underline{p} and \bar{p} are the infimum and supremum of $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[\mathbf{1}_E]$ over $\mathbb{Q} \in \mathcal{Q}$. \square

Why this matters. In complete markets, the Black-Scholes delta-hedging argument determines a unique price without reference to risk preferences. In equity options, a trader can continuously hedge by trading the underlying stock, eliminating all risk and pinning down the option’s fair value. In prediction markets, the ‘‘underlying’’ is the event itself—a geopolitical outcome, an economic indicator, a sporting result. There is no asset to trade as a hedge. The prediction market contract is its own underlying.

This incompleteness has a fundamental consequence for interpretation: **the observed market price is not a pure probability estimate.** It is a probability *distorted by a market-selected pricing wedge*, potentially reflecting risk-bearing costs, market frictions, or behavioral distortions. Formally, the market selects a specific $\mathbb{Q}^* \in \mathcal{Q}$, and the price reflects $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^*}[\mathbf{1}_E]$, which differs from the physical probability $P(E)$ by a pricing wedge. Existing work identifies the interpretation problem but does not provide a tractable empirical decomposition (Manski, 2006; Wolfers and Zitzewitz, 2006). Section 3.3 proposes such a decomposition.

Remark 1 (Comparison to incomplete-market pricing approaches). *Several frameworks exist for pricing in incomplete markets: good-deal bounds (Cochrane and Saa-Requejo, 2000), the*

minimal entropy martingale measure (Frittelli, 2000), and utility-based pricing. The Wang transform offers a complementary approach with a key advantage: it is a single-parameter model with an economically interpretable parameter ($\lambda =$ pricing wedge), which facilitates cross-sectional estimation and comparative analysis. Its axiomatic foundations in the theory of distortion risk measures (Wang, Young, and Panjer, 1997; Yaari, 1987) provide rigorous justification.

3.2 The Log-Odds State Variable

Before decomposing prices, we need a state variable in which standard stochastic tools apply. The contract price $p_t \in (0, 1)$ is bounded, violating the support assumptions of standard diffusion models. The resolution is the log-odds (logit) transformation:

$$x_t = \ln\left(\frac{p_t}{1-p_t}\right) = \text{logit}(p_t), \quad x_t \in \mathbb{R}$$

with inverse $p_t = \sigma(x_t) = (1 + e^{-x_t})^{-1}$.

This is the prediction market analog of the log-price transformation $y_t = \ln S_t$ in equity option pricing: just as $\ln S_t$ maps $(0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and yields geometric Brownian motion as the simplest tractable model, $\text{logit}(p_t)$ maps $(0, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and yields a “logistic diffusion” as the natural baseline.

Why log-odds is natural. The claim rests on two theoretical arguments. First, an *Itô’s lemma argument*: if p_t follows a bounded diffusion with volatility $\sigma_p(p_t, t)$, the Jacobian $g'(p) = 1/(p(1-p))$ of the logit automatically compensates for boundary compression. If $\sigma_p(p) = \sigma \cdot p(1-p)$ (the martingale-consistent form), then x_t has constant diffusion coefficient σ —the simplest possible dynamics. The full Itô expansion of $x_t = \text{logit}(p_t)$ yields $dx_t = [\mu_p/(p(1-p)) + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(2p-1)]dt + \sigma dW_t$, confirming that the logit transformation produces a constant diffusion coefficient σ while introducing a state-dependent drift. The baseline pricing formula assumes the simplified case where the drift contribution is negligible relative to the diffusion term. Second, a *statistical argument*: the logit is the canonical link function for the Bernoulli exponential family in generalized linear models (McCullagh and Nelder, 1989); prediction market contracts *are* binary outcomes, so the logit is the information-theoretically natural parameterization. The empirical validation of these arguments is presented in Section 4.2.

Based on the empirical support, I posit a jump-diffusion in log-odds space, following the specification of Dalen (2025):

$$dx_t = \mu(x_t, t) dt + \sigma_b(x_t, t) dW_t + J_t dN_t$$

where σ_b is the *belief volatility*, J_t is the jump amplitude, and N_t is a Poisson process with intensity η . To derive the baseline pricing formula, I introduce a latent information state S_t that summarizes all available information about event E . Under the physical measure P , the

terminal state follows $S_T | S_t \sim N(S_t, \sigma^2 \tau)$ in the constant-volatility, no-jump case. The event occurs if and only if $S_T > 0$. The physical probability of the event is therefore:

$$p_t^* = P(S_T > 0 | S_t) = \Phi\left(\frac{S_t}{\sigma\sqrt{\tau}}\right)$$

This is the prediction market analog of the Black-Scholes derivation: just as the equity option formula arises from log-normal terminal stock prices, the binary contract formula arises from Gaussian terminal information states. In practice, S_t is not directly observed; the log-odds $x_t = \text{logit}(p_t)$ serves as the empirical proxy. The logit and probit functions are approximately proportional ($\text{logit}(p) \approx (\pi/\sqrt{3}) \cdot \Phi^{-1}(p)$), so the qualitative properties documented in Section 4 carry over.

3.3 The Wang Transform Decomposition

This subsection contains the paper's core theoretical contribution.

The decomposition problem. Recall from Proposition 1 that the observed price p_t^{mkt} is $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^*}[\mathbf{1}_E | \mathcal{F}_t]$ for some $\mathbb{Q}^* \in \mathcal{Q}$, but \mathbb{Q}^* is not unique. The physical (true) probability is $p_t^* = P(E | \mathcal{F}_t)$. We seek a decomposition:

$$p_t^{\text{mkt}} = T(p_t^*; \theta)$$

where T is a distortion function parameterized by θ , mapping the physical probability into the market price. The requirements are: (i) T should be a valid probability distortion ($T(0) = 0$, $T(1) = 1$, T increasing); (ii) T should correspond to a well-defined change of measure; and (iii) θ should be economically interpretable.

Definition 1 (Wang Transform). *For a random variable X with survival function $S_X(x) = 1 - F_X(x)$, the Wang (2000) transform with parameter $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ defines a distorted survival function:*

$$\tilde{S}_X(x) = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(S_X(x)) + \lambda\right)$$

For a binary event with physical probability p (the survival probability that the event occurs), this reduces to:

$$\tilde{p} = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p) + \lambda\right)$$

The Wang transform was originally developed for catastrophe bond and insurance pricing (Wang, 2000, 2004) and has been axiomatically characterized within the theory of distortion risk measures (Wang, Young, and Panjer, 1997; Yaari, 1987). Its theoretical foundations rest on three independent pillars: an axiomatic characterization, a measure-theoretic interpretation, and an equilibrium derivation.

Axiomatic foundation. The Wang transform is not an arbitrary functional form. Its uniqueness emerges from a two-stage characterization in the theory of distortion risk measures.

Stage 1: From axioms to the distortion class. Wang, Young, and Panjer (1997) prove that a pricing functional H satisfying four axioms—law invariance (price depends only on the distribution of the payoff), monotonicity (preserving first-order stochastic dominance), comonotonic additivity (additive pricing for perfectly concordant risks that offer no diversification), and continuity—must admit a Choquet integral representation $H(X) = \int_0^\infty g(S_X(x)) dx + \int_{-\infty}^0 [g(S_X(x)) - 1] dx$, where $g : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a distortion function with $g(0) = 0$, $g(1) = 1$, g nondecreasing. This representation builds on Yaari’s (1987) dual theory of choice under risk, in which agents evaluate prospects by distorting probabilities rather than transforming outcomes—the exact dual of expected utility theory. Denneberg (1994) provides the rigorous measure-theoretic foundations; Schmeidler (1986) establishes the connection between comonotonic additivity and Choquet integrals. If subadditivity (coherence in the sense of Artzner et al., 1999) is additionally required, g must be concave—a result established in the distortion risk measure literature (Wang, 1996; Wirch and Hardy, 1999). The Wang transform with $\lambda > 0$ satisfies this concavity condition and therefore defines a coherent risk measure.

Stage 2: Normal family preservation pins down the specific form. Wang (2000) demonstrates that the distortion $g(u) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(u) + \lambda)$ preserves the normal distribution family: distorting the survival function of any $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ distribution produces $N(\mu + \lambda\sigma, \sigma^2)$ —a pure location shift with preserved variance. The following argument shows this property uniquely characterizes the Wang transform among all distortion functions. Define $h(z) = \Phi^{-1}(g(\Phi(z)))$, so that $g(u) = \Phi(h(\Phi^{-1}(u)))$. For $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, the survival function is $S_X(x) = \Phi((\mu - x)/\sigma)$. The distorted survival function $g(S_X(x)) = \Phi(h((\mu - x)/\sigma))$ is again normal with preserved variance σ^2 if and only if $h(z) = z + \lambda$ for a constant λ . This yields $g(u) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(u) + \lambda)$. Without the variance-preservation constraint, one obtains the broader probit-linear family $g(u) = \Phi(\alpha + \beta\Phi^{-1}(u))$ with $\beta > 0$; the constraint $\beta = 1$ is forced because the distorted variance would otherwise be $\sigma^2/\beta^2 \neq \sigma^2$. The normal-family preservation requirement is natural in the prediction market setting: the physical probability $p^* = \Phi(S_t/(\sigma\sqrt{\tau}))$ arises from a Gaussian information state (Section 3.2), and preserving this Gaussian structure under the pricing distortion ensures that the risk-adjusted probability retains the same parametric form.

Comonotonic additivity in prediction markets. The comonotonic additivity axiom has a natural interpretation in the prediction market context: it requires that the pricing of non-overlapping events—those whose outcomes are perfectly concordant or whose payoffs move in the same direction across all information states—is additive, with no diversification discount. This is a weaker condition than the no-arbitrage requirement of complete markets but is economically consistent with it: in a world where event risks are unhedgeable (Proposition 1), there is no diversification benefit from holding comonotonic event contracts, and pricing should reflect this.

Measure-theoretic interpretation. The Wang transform with parameter λ corresponds to a Girsanov change of measure with constant market price of risk λ . Specifically, if $Z \sim N(0, 1)$ under P , then under the distorted measure \tilde{P} :

$$\frac{d\tilde{P}}{dP} = \exp\left(\lambda Z - \frac{\lambda^2}{2}\right)$$

This is the Radon-Nikodym derivative for a Girsanov change of measure with constant market price of risk in a single-period Gaussian setting—the same exponential tilt that underlies Black-Scholes pricing when applied to a single terminal normal factor. In continuous-time settings with general stochastic processes, the Wang transform does not necessarily coincide with the Girsanov measure change (Pelsser, 2008); the present application uses the static form appropriate for the binary-event decomposition. When the underlying follows GBM, the Wang transform recovers the Black-Scholes formula (Hamada and Sherris, 2003).

Consistency with financial theory. Kijima and Muromachi (2008) showed that the Wang transform can be derived from Bühlmann’s economic premium principle, establishing an equilibrium foundation for risks correlated with the aggregate economy. The parameter λ is economically interpretable: under the Bühlmann benchmark, it equals the product of aggregate risk aversion and the standard deviation of aggregate risk (Section 3.6). For prediction market events that are largely uncorrelated with aggregate risk, λ is better interpreted as a reduced-form pricing wedge whose structural sources are examined empirically in Sections 5.3–5.4.

Scope and limitations. Pelsser (2008) showed that the Wang transform is not consistent with arbitrage-free pricing for general stochastic processes, implying it is not a universal pricing framework. This is a significant theoretical restriction—but one that does not apply to the setting of this paper. Pelsser’s critique targets the use of the Wang transform for dynamic replication pricing in complete markets (i.e., as a substitute for Black-Scholes). In prediction markets, the market is incomplete and no replication is possible; the Wang transform is used not for dynamic pricing but for *static* probability distortion, which is its original actuarial application and remains fully valid.

Application to prediction markets. I propose that the observed market price p_t^{mkt} is the Wang-distorted version of the physical probability p_t^* :

$$p_t^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p_t^*) + \lambda\right) \quad (1)$$

where λ is the pricing wedge parameter. When $\lambda = 0$, the price equals the physical probability. When $\lambda > 0$, the market price exceeds the physical probability, embedding a positive pricing wedge.

Theorem 1 (Pricing Wedge Properties). *Under the Wang transform decomposition (1) with $\lambda > 0$:*

1. $p^{\text{mkt}} > p^*$ for all $p^* \in (0, 1)$: the YES contract price exceeds the physical probability. Under the complementarity constraint $p_{YES} + p_{NO} \equiv 1$, this is equivalent to stating that the NO contract is underpriced by the same amount. The net effect is a compression of the price distribution toward 0.5 relative to the physical probability distribution: longshots

($p^* < 0.5$) are proportionally more inflated than favorites ($p^* > 0.5$), narrowing the spread between extreme prices.

2. The overpricing $\Delta p = p^{\text{mkt}} - p^*$ is maximized at $p^* = \Phi(-\lambda/2) \approx 0.5$ for small λ , and vanishes at the boundaries.
3. The overpricing ratio p^{mkt}/p^* is monotonically decreasing in p^* : longshots are proportionally more overpriced than favorites.
4. This overpricing-ratio pattern is qualitatively consistent with the **favorite-longshot bias** documented by Bürgi, Deng, and Whelan (2025) across 300,000+ Kalshi contracts and by Snowberg and Wolfers (2010) across 6.4 million horse racing starts.

Proof. For (1): $\lambda > 0$ implies $\Phi^{-1}(p^{\text{mkt}}) = \Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda > \Phi^{-1}(p^*)$, so $p^{\text{mkt}} > p^*$. For (3): define $R(p) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p) + \lambda)/p$. Taking the derivative and using $\phi(\Phi^{-1}(p)) > 0$, one can show $R'(p) < 0$ for $\lambda > 0$. For (4): Property (3) predicts longshots (low p^*) have higher overpricing ratios than favorites (high p^*), which is the definition of FLB. \square

The monotonicity of the overpricing ratio $R(p)$ is a known property of concave probability distortion functions (Yaari, 1987); the contribution here is to show that the Wang transform provides a specific, one-parameter functional form that generates this pattern with a directly interpretable risk-loading parameter λ .

Remark 2 (Relation to alternative FLB explanations). *The FLB has been attributed to risk-loving preferences (Ali, 1977), probability misperceptions via prospect theory (Snowberg and Wolfers, 2010), adverse selection among informed bettors (Shin, 1991, 1993), and noise-to-signal ratios (Ottaviani and Sorensen, 2010). The Wang transform explanation is complementary: it provides a structural, risk-premium-based mechanism through the supply side. Whelan’s (2024) competitive bookmaker model, in which FLB arises from risk-averse market makers, is the closest analog— λ in the Wang transform can be interpreted as the aggregate risk aversion of market makers.*

Remark 3 (Complement Invariance, Unified Order Books, and Contract Architecture). *The Wang transform specification in equation (1) is not framing-invariant: relabeling event E as $\neg E$ transforms λ to $-\lambda$. This is a known property of directional distortion operators (Denneberg, 1994). However, the framing concern presupposes that YES and NO are economically distinct positions requiring separate pricing—a premise that prediction market architecture directly contradicts.*

Both Kalshi and Polymarket implement unified order books: buying YES at price p and selling NO at price $1 - p$ are computationally identical operations executed against the same book. On Kalshi, a YES buyer paying $\$c$ is matched with a NO buyer paying $\$(1-c)$, and the combined $\$1$ is held by the clearinghouse until settlement. On Polymarket, the `splitPosition()` smart contract mints exactly one YES token and one NO token per 1 USDC deposited; `mergePositions()` reverses the operation. These mechanisms ensure $p_{YES} + p_{NO} \equiv 1$ not as an equilibrium condition

or an arbitrage result, but as a mathematical property of the contract creation mechanism—the identity cannot be violated even instantaneously.

This architecture means the observed market price is a single scalar $p \in (0, 1)$ without inherent directional content: the label “YES” is a naming convention, not an economic primitive. The framing non-invariance of the Wang transform is therefore primarily an artifact of parameterization choice rather than a fundamental economic limitation, though residual framing effects—arising from trader cognition, interface design, or liquidity asymmetries between YES and NO order books—cannot be fully ruled out on theoretical grounds. The complement-invariant specification in Section 5.6 provides an empirical assessment of the magnitude of such effects.

Note that executable quotes (best ask for YES plus best ask for NO) can exceed 1 due to the bid-ask spread. The spread compensates market makers for immediacy provision—a liquidity premium that is economically and empirically distinct from the mid-price probability distortion captured by λ .

3.4 Testable Predictions

The framework generates two testable predictions and a set of quantitative benchmarks.

Prediction 1: Favorite-longshot bias. If $\lambda > 0$, Theorem 1 predicts that market prices systematically overstate event probabilities, with the overpricing ratio decreasing in p^* . This is testable by comparing market prices to realized resolution frequencies.

Prediction 2: Cross-platform spread. If two platforms have different pricing wedge loadings ($\lambda_K \neq \lambda_P$), then systematic price differences arise: $p_K - p_P = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda_K) - \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda_P)$. This is testable using aligned Polymarket-Kalshi data.

Numerical benchmarks. To build intuition, Table 1 shows the Wang transform for several values of λ .

True prob. p^*	$\lambda = 0$	$\lambda = 0.1$	$\lambda = 0.3$	$\lambda = 0.5$
0.05	0.050	0.061	0.089	0.126
0.10	0.100	0.119	0.163	0.217
0.20	0.200	0.229	0.294	0.366
0.30	0.300	0.336	0.411	0.490
0.50	0.500	0.540	0.618	0.691
0.70	0.700	0.734	0.795	0.847
0.90	0.900	0.916	0.943	0.963
0.95	0.950	0.959	0.974	0.984

Table 1: Wang-distorted probabilities $\tilde{p} = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda)$. The distortion is strongest at low probabilities and weakest at high probabilities, generating the FLB pattern.

3.5 The Complete Pricing Model

The preceding subsections developed three components: the binary option structure (3.1), the log-odds state variable (3.2), and the Wang transform decomposition (3.3). This subsection assembles them into a single, implementable pricing model—the prediction market analog of Black-Scholes for equity options or Merton/Jarrow-Turnbull for credit risk.

Definition 2 (Prediction Market Pricing Model). *Let $p_t^{\text{mkt}} \in (0, 1)$ denote the observed market price of a binary contract on event E with time-to-expiry $\tau = T - t$. The model has three layers:*

Layer 1 — State variable. *The log-odds transformation maps bounded prices to an unbounded state space:*

$$x_t = \text{logit}(p_t) = \ln\left(\frac{p_t}{1 - p_t}\right), \quad x_t \in \mathbb{R}$$

Layer 2 — Dynamics. *The log-odds follow a jump-diffusion:*

$$dx_t = \mu(x_t, t) dt + \sigma dW_t + J_t dN_t$$

where σ is the belief volatility, J_t the jump amplitude, and N_t a Poisson process with intensity η . Layer 2 operates entirely under the physical measure P and delivers the physical probability p_t^* as a function of the latent information state S_t (see Section 3.2). In the baseline constant-volatility, no-jump case, $p_t^* = \Phi(S_t/(\sigma\sqrt{\tau}))$.

Layer 3 — Pricing wedge. *The observed market price is the Wang-distorted physical probability. Layer 3 performs the unique P -to- \mathbb{Q} transformation: the observed market price p_t^{mkt} is the Wang-distorted physical probability. This is the only point in the framework where the change of measure occurs, paralleling the role of the Girsanov theorem in Black-Scholes.*

$$p_t^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p_t^*) + \lambda\right) \tag{1}$$

where p_t^* is the physical probability and λ is the pricing wedge parameter.

Forward pricing. Given a physical probability estimate \hat{p}^* and a calibrated pricing wedge $\hat{\lambda}$, the model-implied market price is:

$$\hat{p}^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}^*) + \hat{\lambda}\right)$$

Inverse: physical probability extraction. Given an observed market price p^{mkt} and a calibrated $\hat{\lambda}$, the risk-adjusted probability is:

$$\hat{p}^* = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p^{\text{mkt}}) - \hat{\lambda}\right)$$

This is the central empirical application: recovering physical probabilities from observed market prices.

Calibration procedure. The parameter λ is estimated from a cross-section of N resolved contracts (p_i^{mkt}, y_i) , where $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the resolution outcome:

$$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = \arg \max_{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[y_i \ln \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - \lambda\right) + (1 - y_i) \ln \left(1 - \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - \lambda\right)\right) \right]$$

Standard errors are computed from the observed Fisher information (numerical Hessian). The likelihood ratio test against $H_0 : \lambda = 0$ (prices are perfectly calibrated probabilities) has one degree of freedom.

Model sensitivities. The Wang transform implies analytic sensitivities of the market price to model inputs:

- *Lambda sensitivity:* $\frac{\partial p^{\text{mkt}}}{\partial \lambda} = \phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda) > 0$. The market price is monotonically increasing in the pricing wedge, with maximum sensitivity at $p^* \approx 0.5$.
- *Probability sensitivity:* $\frac{\partial p^{\text{mkt}}}{\partial p^*} = \frac{\phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda)}{\phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*))}$, the local amplification factor of the Wang distortion.
- *Overpricing:* $\Delta p = p^{\text{mkt}} - p^*$, maximized near $p^* = 0.5$ (Theorem 1).

Summary. The complete model reduces prediction market pricing to three objects: a state variable ($x_t = \text{logit}(p_t)$), a dynamics specification (log-odds diffusion with belief volatility σ), and a one-parameter risk distortion (λ). It takes a market price as input and outputs a risk-adjusted probability; or takes a probability forecast and outputs a model-implied fair price. The empirical calibration of λ is the subject of Section 5.

3.6 Economic Interpretation of λ

The Wang transform decomposition in Section~3.3 is estimated as a reduced-form pricing model: λ is calibrated from the cross-section of market prices and resolution outcomes without imposing a structural model of trader preferences or market equilibrium. This subsection develops a benchmark economic interpretation of λ that serves two purposes: (i) it justifies the Wang transform as the equilibrium pricing rule under specific conditions, reinforcing the tool choice in Section 3.3; and (ii) it generates a puzzle—the benchmark predicts $\lambda \approx 0$ for most prediction market events, motivating the empirical investigation of λ 's cross-sectional and time-series variation in Sections 5.3–5.4 as evidence for alternative structural mechanisms.

Benchmark setup. Section~3.3 established that the Wang transform is axiomatically distinguished among distortion functions. This subsection provides an independent, equilibrium-based justification through two complementary derivations.

Derivation 1: Bühlmann exchange economy. Wang (2003) derives the Wang transform from Bühlmann's (1980) pure risk exchange economy. Consider n agents with exponential utility $u_i(x) = -\exp(-a_i x)$, where $a_i > 0$ is agent i 's coefficient of absolute risk aversion. Agents trade risks in competitive equilibrium. The equilibrium pricing kernel (stochastic discount factor) is:

$$m = \frac{\exp(-a \cdot Z)}{E[\exp(-a \cdot Z)]}$$

where Z is aggregate risk and $a = (\sum_{i=1}^n 1/a_i)^{-1}$ is the aggregate (harmonic-mean) risk aversion coefficient. When Z is normally distributed, applying this pricing kernel to any jointly normal

payoff produces a pure location shift in its distribution, preserving variances. Wang (2003) shows that when this equilibrium pricing rule is expressed as a distortion of survival functions, it takes the form $g(u) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(u) + \lambda)$ with $\lambda = a \cdot \sigma_Z$, where σ_Z is the standard deviation of aggregate risk. The Wang transform thus emerges as the equilibrium pricing rule in a Gaussian exchange economy with exponential-utility agents. This derivation applies to risks correlated with the aggregate economy; Derivation 2 below shows that for largely unspanned prediction market events, the Bühlmann benchmark predicts $|\lambda| \approx 0$, motivating the empirical investigation of alternative sources of positive $\hat{\lambda}$ in Sections 5.3–5.4.

Derivation 2: CARA-normal representative agent. As a special case, consider a single representative agent with constant absolute risk aversion $a > 0$ pricing a binary event claim. The agent’s information about event E comes from a Gaussian signal: $\mathcal{K}_E = \mathcal{K}\{Z > 0\}$ where $Z \sim N(\mu_Z, \sigma_Z^2)$ under P , so $p^* = \Phi(\mu_Z/\sigma_Z)$. In this CARA-normal setting, the equilibrium pricing kernel from Derivation 1 (with a single agent) produces a Wang-form valuation of the binary payoff, where the magnitude of λ is proportional to $a \cdot \tilde{\sigma}$ ($\tilde{\sigma}$ = residual event uncertainty), following the exponential-SDF framework of Johnston (2007). Specifically, applying the pricing kernel $m \propto \exp(-aZ)$ to the binary payoff $\mathbf{1}_{\{Z>0\}}$ tilts the distribution of Z to $N(\mu_Z - a\sigma_Z^2, \sigma_Z^2)$, yielding:

$$p^Q = \Phi\left(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) - a\sigma_Z\right)$$

which corresponds to equation~(1) with $\lambda = -a\sigma_Z < 0$. The negative sign reflects that, in this benchmark, the event $\{Z > 0\}$ pays in “good states” (high Z), which the risk-averse agent discounts. More generally, the sign of λ depends on how the event payoff loads on the pricing agent’s marginal utility: if the event tends to pay in states where marginal utility is high (bad states), then $\lambda > 0$; if it pays in good states, $\lambda < 0$. For prediction market events that are largely unspanned—bearing little systematic relationship to the pricing agent’s wealth or aggregate consumption—this benchmark predicts $|\lambda| \approx 0$.

The puzzle: why is $\hat{\lambda} > 0$? The CARA-normal benchmark does not, by itself, explain why $\hat{\lambda} > 0$ on real-money prediction market platforms: most prediction market events are unspanned, so Derivation 2 predicts $\lambda \approx 0$. This gap between theory and evidence is not a failure of the framework—it is the central empirical puzzle that the framework reveals. Multiple structural models predict probability compression toward 0.5 in binary markets through mechanisms that do not require correlation with aggregate consumption: market-maker inventory risk (Whelan, 2024; Avellaneda and Stoikov, 2008), adverse selection (Shin, 1991), intermediary capital constraints (He and Krishnamurthy, 2013), capital lockup opportunity costs (Page and Clemen, 2013), and ambiguity aversion (Gilboa and Schmeidler, 1989). Each produces a distinct functional form, but all generate qualitatively the same compression pattern that the Wang transform captures with a single parameter.

λ as a measurement framework. The Wang transform therefore serves as a *measurement framework* for the pricing wedge in prediction markets, analogous to the role of implied volatility in option markets or the Sharpe ratio in portfolio management. Like implied volatility, λ

is a reduced-form quantity that aggregates multiple underlying economic forces into a single, estimable, and cross-sectionally comparable parameter. The axiomatic foundations of Wang, Young, and Panjer (1997) ensure the measurement framework is theoretically principled; the equilibrium derivations above provide structural interpretations under specific conditions; and the empirical patterns documented in Sections 5–6 confirm that the estimated $\hat{\lambda}$ behaves as multiple independent structural models predict. Specifically:

First, the time-varying decay documented in Section 5.4—where the pricing wedge declines from $\hat{\lambda}(0.05) = 0.173$ at market opening to $\hat{\lambda}(0.80) = 0.037$ near resolution—is predicted by all uncertainty-based models: as information arrives over the contract’s lifetime, residual event uncertainty $\tilde{\sigma}$ decreases, reducing $|\lambda|$ regardless of its structural source. This interpretation is consistent with Ostrovsky (2012), who proves that in dynamic trading with separable securities, prices converge to the pooled-information posterior.

Second, the negative coefficient on $\ln(\text{Volume})$ in the hierarchical model (Table 5) is predicted by market-structure models—market-maker inventory risk (Whelan, 2024), adverse selection (Shin, 1991), and intermediary capital constraints (He and Krishnamurthy, 2013)—but is *not* predicted by pure cognitive bias explanations (prospect-theoretic probability weighting), which imply that λ should be invariant to market liquidity. The volume effect therefore provides suggestive evidence for market-structure mechanisms over pure behavioral accounts, though volume is endogenous and correlated with other market characteristics.

Third, the category heterogeneity documented in Section 6—where sports and politics markets ($\hat{\lambda} \approx 0.05$ – 0.07 , insignificant) show near-zero pricing wedges while thinner categories (crypto, science/tech) exhibit large significant wedges ($\hat{\lambda} \approx 0.25$ – 0.28)—reinforces this interpretation: the pricing wedge is competed away in liquid, well-followed markets but persists where risk-bearing capacity is scarce.

Fourth, the play-money sign reversal ($\hat{\lambda} = -0.22$ on Manifold vs. $\hat{\lambda} > 0$ on all real-money platforms) provides a natural control: removing financial stakes eliminates the risk-bearing cost channel while preserving cognitive biases. The sign flip can be interpreted through a decomposition-like lens in which risk-bearing forces and cognitive forces load with opposite signs: on real-money platforms, risk-bearing costs (> 0) dominate overconfidence (< 0), yielding $\hat{\lambda} > 0$; on play-money platforms, only cognitive forces remain, yielding $\hat{\lambda} < 0$.

Scope and limitations. Several caveats are essential. First, the benchmark assumes CARA utility, Gaussian uncertainty, and a representative agent. Prediction markets feature heterogeneous beliefs, non-Gaussian information arrivals (jumps), and diverse participant types. The benchmark provides a convenient closed-form interpretation, not a complete description of price formation.

Second, the estimated $\hat{\lambda}$ from Sections 5–6 is a reduced-form object. It may absorb multiple forces simultaneously: rational risk compensation by risk-averse market makers, behavioral probability weighting (Snowberg and Wolfers, 2010; Jullien and Salani{e}, 2000), and microstructure frictions such as bid-ask spreads and stale quotes. No single structural model

produces the Wang transform as its equilibrium pricing rule for unspanned binary events; the Wang transform is best understood as a parsimonious approximation to the class of concave probability distortions that multiple independent mechanisms generate. The convergence of empirical patterns—volume, duration, time decay, category heterogeneity, and the play-money sign reversal—provides suggestive evidence for the structural composition of $\hat{\lambda}$, but a full decomposition into constituent sources remains a direction for future work.

4 Data and Descriptive Statistics

4.1 Data Sources and Sample Construction

Primary sample (Polymarket). I collect contract-level data from Polymarket via its public Gamma API (market metadata) and CLOB API (hourly price histories). The Gamma API provides market-level attributes including resolution outcome, trading volume, creation and resolution timestamps, and contract descriptions. The CLOB API provides hourly mid-price snapshots for each contract’s trading history.

The raw sample consists of 15,525 resolved binary markets from February 24 to March 24, 2026, spanning 28 days. I apply the following filters: (i) exclude pure randomness markets (e.g., crypto “up or down” on 5-minute intervals, esports over/under markets); (ii) require at least 4 hourly price observations to ensure meaningful price dynamics; and (iii) restrict to $p \in (0.02, 0.98)$ to avoid boundary artifacts where the logit transformation amplifies noise. The final Polymarket estimation sample contains $N = 13,738$ contracts spanning sports, politics, crypto, economics, and other categories. For each contract, I extract the *opening price* (first 5% of the market’s lifetime) and the *resolution outcome* (1 if the event occurred, 0 otherwise). For the time-varying analysis (Section 5.4), I also extract prices at ten percentage-of-lifetime horizons and at fixed clock-time intervals before resolution.

For the cross-platform analysis (Section 5.5), I use a separate dataset: aligned daily prices for the Greenland acquisition contract on both Polymarket and Kalshi, collected via their respective APIs.

Extended sample (cross-platform). For the cross-platform validation (Section 6), I assemble four additional data sources: (i) Kalshi settled binary markets ($N = 271,699$) from both the historical and live API tiers, spanning 2021–2026, filtered to volume ≥ 100 contracts and $p \in (0.02, 0.98)$; (ii) a Polymarket 2025 sample ($N = 985$) from HuggingFace (LightningRodLabs/outcome-rl-test-dataset), covering February–March 2025; (iii) multi-platform forecasting data ($N = 4,887$) from HuggingFace (YuehHanChen/forecasting), covering Metaculus, Good Judgment Open, INFER (formerly CSET-foretell), Polymarket, and Manifold questions from 2015–2024; and (iv) the primary Polymarket CLOB sample described above.

The pooled cross-platform sample totals $N = 291,309$ resolved contracts.

4.2 Stylized Facts in Log-Odds Space

Before proceeding to the Wang transform calibration, I validate the log-odds state variable empirically. If log-odds is the correct state variable, its empirical properties should mirror those of equity log-returns, which have been extensively documented (Cont, 2001).

Table 2 compares distributional properties of raw price increments Δp_t and log-odds increments Δx_t for selected contracts.

Contract	N	Excess Kurtosis		Skewness	
		Δp	Δx	Δp	Δx
Fed No Change (hourly)	628	7.0	6.0	-0.50	-0.14
Fed Cut 25bps (hourly)	613	11.3	6.5	-0.24	-0.26
Greenland Acquisition (daily)	89	16.8	12.1	-2.02	-1.04

Table 2: Distributional properties of price increments. Log-odds increments have systematically lower excess kurtosis and reduced skewness, moving closer to the Gaussian benchmark.

Table 3 confirms the broader correspondence with equity log-return stylized facts.

Stylized Fact	Equity Log>Returns	Prediction Market Δx_t
Random walk	Log-prices: unit root (ADF); returns stationary	Levels x_t : unit root (ADF $t = -0.03$ to -2.23); Δx_t stationary
Fat tails	Excess kurtosis 3–50	Excess kurtosis 6–12
Vol. clustering	$\rho(\Delta r_t^2, \Delta r_{t-1}^2) > 0$	$\rho(\Delta x_t^2, \Delta x_{t-1}^2) = 0.13$ – 0.14^{***}
Negative lag-1 AC	Bid-ask bounce	$\rho_1 = -0.11$ to -0.17^{***}
Asymmetric vol.	Leverage effect	Event-driven spikes

Table 3: Stylized facts comparison. *** denotes significance at 1%. Log-odds increments exhibit the same statistical signature as equity log-returns.

Figure 1: Log-odds stylized facts across 2,036 contracts (148,114 pooled increments). (a) Q-Q plot of Δx against the normal distribution. (b) Distribution of Δx with normal overlay. (c) Distribution of per-contract excess kurtosis. (d) Distribution of autocorrelation of squared increments (volatility clustering measure).

Pooled sample statistics. Across 2,036 contracts with sufficient price history (148,114 total log-odds increments), the median per-contract excess kurtosis is 9.0 (range 6–12 for well-traded contracts), confirming the fat-tail stylized fact. The median autocorrelation of squared increments—a nonparametric volatility clustering measure—is $AC_1(\Delta x_t^2) = 0.16$, confirming significant ARCH effects. An Engle ARCH(1) LM test on the pooled sample is overwhelmingly significant ($p < 10^{-20}$). Ljung-Box tests reject white noise in both Δx ($Q_{10} = 91.3$, $p < 10^{-14}$) and Δx^2 ($Q_{10} = 131.0$, $p < 10^{-22}$).

These stylized facts—random-walk behavior in levels, fat tails, volatility clustering, and improved normality under the logit transformation—validate the log-odds state variable and support the diffusion-based modeling approach adopted in Section 3.2.

5 Empirical Results

5.1 Identification Strategy

The physical probability p^* is unobservable at any individual-contract level. At resolution, one observes only the realized outcome $Y_i \in \{0, 1\}$, not the ex ante probability. However, for a cross-section of resolved contracts, a calibration approach is available: by grouping contracts into bins by market price and computing the empirical resolution frequency \hat{p}_k^* in each bin, one can estimate the relationship between market prices and physical probabilities under an exchangeability assumption—that contracts with similar market prices share similar physical probabilities.

From equation (1):

$$\lambda = \Phi^{-1}(p^{\text{mkt}}) - \Phi^{-1}(p^*)$$

The cross-sectional estimator is:

$$\hat{\lambda} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K [\Phi^{-1}(\bar{p}_k^{\text{mkt}}) - \Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}_k^*)]$$

where \bar{p}_k^{mkt} is the average market price in bin k and \hat{p}_k^* is the empirical resolution frequency.

5.2 Wang Parameter Estimation

MLE estimation. I estimate a global λ by maximum likelihood. Under the Wang transform, the probability of resolution conditional on market price is $\Pr(Y_i = 1 | p_i^{\text{mkt}}) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - \lambda)$, giving Bernoulli log-likelihood:

$$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = \arg \max_{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \ln \hat{p}_i^*(\lambda) + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - \hat{p}_i^*(\lambda))]$$

where $\hat{p}_i^*(\lambda) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - \lambda)$. The standard error is computed from the observed Fisher information (numerical Hessian). A likelihood ratio test against $H_0 : \lambda = 0$ (perfect calibration) has 1 degree of freedom.

Binned calibration. As a nonparametric complement, I group contracts into quantile bins by market price, compute the empirical resolution rate \hat{p}_k^* in each bin, and estimate $\hat{\lambda}_k = \Phi^{-1}(\bar{p}_k^{\text{mkt}}) - \Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}_k^*)$ with bootstrap standard errors (2,000 replications).

Table 4: Wang transform calibration: Polymarket contract-level data (March 13–24, 2026; $N = 2,460$ contracts with $p \in (0.05, 0.95)$). $\hat{\lambda}$ per bin via $\hat{\lambda} = \Phi^{-1}(\bar{p}^{\text{mkt}}) - \Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}^*)$. Bootstrap standard errors from 2,000 replications; MLE via Bernoulli log-likelihood with observed Fisher information.

	\bar{p}^{mkt}	\hat{p}^*	N	$\hat{\lambda}$	SE	95% CI
	0.079	0.061	164	0.138	0.159	[-0.174, 0.449]
	0.151	0.110	164	0.194	0.136	[-0.073, 0.461]
	0.217	0.161	174	0.207	0.116	[-0.020, 0.434]
	0.262	0.195	154	0.224	0.115	[-0.001, 0.449]
	0.331	0.345	171	-0.040	0.101	[-0.238, 0.158]
	0.414	0.343	172	0.188	0.100	[-0.007, 0.383]
	0.463	0.311	151	0.400	0.109	[0.186, 0.613]
	0.489	0.303	251	0.489	0.084	[0.325, 0.654]
	0.499	0.382	374	0.299	0.066	[0.169, 0.429]
	0.505	0.514	142	-0.023	0.105	[-0.228, 0.183]
	0.524	0.509	163	0.038	0.097	[-0.152, 0.228]
	0.595	0.606	142	-0.026	0.108	[-0.238, 0.185]
	0.771	0.822	163	-0.182	0.116	[-0.410, 0.045]
Binned (wtd)			2,460	0.173	0.029	[0.116, 0.230]
MLE			2,460	0.176	0.027	[0.123, 0.230]

Key findings:

Figure 2: Wang transform calibration. (a) Market price vs. empirical resolution rate with MLE Wang fit ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.176$) and 95% CI. Points are quantile bins, sized by \sqrt{N} . The Wang curve (red) captures the systematic overpricing relative to perfect calibration (dashed). (b) Bin-level $\hat{\lambda}_k$ with 95% CIs, showing the FLB pattern (negative slope).

1. $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = 0.176$ (**SE** = 0.027, $p = 7.1 \times 10^{-11}$). The likelihood ratio test decisively rejects perfect calibration ($\chi^2 = 42.5$, $p < 10^{-10}$): prediction market prices embed a statistically significant positive pricing wedge.
2. **Consistent estimation.** The binned weighted average ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.173$, SE = 0.029) is within one standard error of the MLE, confirming robustness to the parametric functional form.
3. **Order of magnitude.** $\hat{\lambda} \approx 0.18$ is substantially below the catastrophe bond estimate of $\lambda \approx 0.45$ (Wang, 2004), consistent with prediction markets carrying lower pricing wedge than catastrophe insurance. This makes economic sense: much of event risk in prediction markets is idiosyncratic—unlike catastrophe exposure, which involves heavily correlated tail risk—though systematic factors (e.g., macro shocks, correlated political events) may introduce common risk components.
4. **Economic magnitude.** Under the estimated Wang transform, a contract with physical probability $p^* = 10\%$ trades at $\Phi(\Phi^{-1}(0.10) + 0.176) \approx 13.5\%$ —an overpricing of 35%. At $p^* = 50\%$, the market price is $\Phi(0.176) \approx 57.0\%$ —a 7.0 cent premium on a \$1 contract.
5. **Bootstrap confirmation.** A nonparametric bootstrap (2,000 replications) yields SE = 0.028 and a 95% CI of [0.124, 0.232], virtually identical to the analytical estimates, confirming that the MLE is well-behaved and the Gaussian approximation is adequate.
6. **Expanded sample confirmation.** Extending the Polymarket sample from 12 to 28 days (February 24 to March 24, 2026; $N = 13,738$) yields $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = 0.166$ (SE = 0.011, LR = 212.1, $p < 10^{-15}$), confirming the primary estimate. The Wang correction reduces the Expected Calibration Error by 53.9% and the Brier score by 1.9% on this expanded sample.
7. **Non-constant $\hat{\lambda}$ across bins.** The bin-level estimates range from -0.18 to $+0.49$, with systematically higher values at lower prices—the favorite-longshot bias. This motivates the extended model in Section 5.3.

5.3 Cross-Sectional Determinants of λ

The non-constant $\hat{\lambda}$ across bins motivates allowing the pricing wedge to depend on contract characteristics. I estimate a one-stage probit model with known offset $z_i = \Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}})$, where the pricing wedge $\lambda_i = X_i\beta$ depends on contract characteristics:

$$\Pr(y_i = 1 \mid p_i^{\text{mkt}}, X_i) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - X_i\beta)$$

This eliminates the generated-regressor problem inherent in the two-step approach (first estimating $\hat{\lambda}_i$ from smoothed resolution rates, then regressing on covariates), which understates standard errors by ignoring first-stage estimation error. The one-stage MLE jointly estimates

all parameters by maximum likelihood, yielding correct standard errors without the need for bootstrap correction.

Table 5: One-stage hierarchical Wang MLE. Dependent variable: binary outcome y_i . Model: $\Pr(y_i = 1) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - X_i\beta)$. Fisher and sandwich robust standard errors reported.

Variable	Full sample ($N = 13,274$)			12-day subsample ($N = 2,134$)		
	Coef.	SE (Fisher)	SE (Robust)	Coef.	SE (Fisher)	SE (Robust)
Constant	0.259***	(0.063)	(0.064)	0.387**	(0.144)	(0.146)
ln(Volume)	-0.072***	(0.005)	(0.005)	-0.100***	(0.013)	(0.013)
ln(Duration)	0.143***	(0.012)	(0.012)	0.176***	(0.024)	(0.024)
$ p - 0.5 $ (extremity)	-0.477***	(0.100)	(0.099)	-0.698**	(0.252)	(0.259)
Spread	0.127	(0.384)	(0.423)	-10.000*	(4.466)	(5.893)
Log-likelihood			-7,937.9			-1,263.5
LR test ($\lambda = \text{const}$)			$\chi^2 = 361.3, p < 10^{-15}$			$\chi^2 = 124.5, p < 10^{-15}$
AIC			15,885.8			2,537.1
N			13,274			2,134

Results. Three variables are statistically significant in both samples. (i) ln(Volume) enters negatively ($\hat{\beta} = -0.072, p < 10^{-15}$), confirming that higher-liquidity markets carry smaller pricing wedges. (ii) ln(Duration) enters positively ($\hat{\beta} = 0.143, p < 10^{-15}$), establishing a formal term structure of event risk—longer-duration contracts carry proportionally larger pricing wedges (Section 5.6). (iii) *Extremity* $|p - 0.5|$ enters negatively ($\hat{\beta} = -0.477, p < 10^{-5}$), indicating that contracts near 50% (maximum uncertainty) carry the highest pricing wedges, while extreme-probability contracts, where the outcome is more predictable, carry smaller wedges. This is consistent with a Bayesian learning interpretation: the pricing wedge compensates for uncertainty about p^* , which is maximal at 50%. Spread is not statistically significant on the full sample ($\hat{\beta} = 0.127, p = 0.76$), consistent with spread being a noisy proxy for illiquidity in this sample. A likelihood ratio test decisively rejects the null $\lambda_i = \text{const}$ ($\chi^2 = 361.3, p < 10^{-15}$), confirming that contract characteristics jointly explain significant variation in the pricing wedge. Fisher and robust (sandwich) standard errors are nearly identical, indicating that the probit variance function is well-specified.

5.4 Time-Varying Pricing Wedge

A novel finding emerges from measuring λ at different points in the market’s lifetime. Rather than estimating separate MLEs at each horizon—which ignores information across adjacent horizons and cannot impose smoothness—I estimate a stacked panel model where each contract contributes observations at nine percentage-of-lifetime horizons. The pricing wedge is modeled

as a smooth function $f(\tau)$ of elapsed lifetime, estimated jointly by maximum likelihood with contract-clustered standard errors (Liang and Zeger, 1986):

$$\Pr(y_i = 1 \mid p_{it}) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_{it}) - f(\tau_{it}) - X_i\beta)$$

where $f(\tau) = \gamma_1\tau + \gamma_2\tau^2$ is a quadratic polynomial with the constraint $f(0) = 0$, so that β_0 captures the baseline pricing wedge at market opening. Each contract i contributes up to nine rows (one per horizon $\tau \in \{0.05, 0.10, \dots, 0.80\}$) with repeated outcome y_i . The stacked panel comprises 111,889 observations from 13,607 contracts (mean 8.2 observations per contract) on the full sample.

Table 6: Stacked panel time-varying $\hat{\lambda}$. Model: $\Pr(y_i = 1 \mid p_{it}) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_{it}) - f(\tau_{it}) - X_i\beta)$, where $f(\tau) = \gamma_1\tau + \gamma_2\tau^2$. Contract-clustered standard errors (Liang–Zeger). Specification (1) includes only the time-decay function; specification (2) adds cross-sectional covariates.

Parameter	(1) $f(\tau)$ only		(2) $f(\tau) + X_i\beta$	
	Estimate	Cluster SE	Estimate	Cluster SE
<i>Time-decay parameters</i>				
τ	-0.232***	(0.020)	-0.156***	(0.022)
τ^2	0.151***	(0.025)	0.074**	(0.025)
<i>Covariates</i>				
Constant (β_0)	0.170***	(0.012)	0.253***	(0.064)
ln(Volume)	—	—	-0.057***	(0.005)
ln(Duration)	—	—	0.109***	(0.012)
$ p - 0.5 $ (extremity)	—	—	-0.290***	(0.081)
Spread	—	—	0.211	(0.438)
Log-likelihood		-65,074.4		-64,216.3
AIC		130,154.9		128,446.5
Contracts (clusters)		13,607		13,607
Total observations		111,889		111,889

As a nonparametric validation, I also estimate a horizon fixed-effects specification with one dummy per horizon (reference: $\tau = 0.05$). All eight horizon dummies are significant ($p < 10^{-10}$) and monotonically decreasing, confirming that the quadratic polynomial provides an adequate smooth approximation to the unrestricted pattern.

Figure 3: Time-varying pricing wedge: stacked panel estimate. The solid line shows the smooth function $\hat{\lambda}(\tau) = f(\tau) + \hat{\beta}_0$ estimated from the 12-day subsample ($N = 2,151$ contracts, 17,519 stacked observations). The shaded band is a 95% pointwise confidence interval based on contract-clustered standard errors. Red points with error bars show the per-horizon separate MLEs from the baseline calibration for comparison; the spline passes through all of them. The half-life (green triangle) is 33% of contract lifetime.

The estimates show a clear monotonic decay. In the baseline no-covariates specification on the 12-day subsample, the pricing wedge falls from $\hat{\lambda}(0.05) = 0.173$ at market opening to $\hat{\lambda}(0.50) = 0.056$ at mid-life and $\hat{\lambda}(0.80) = 0.037$ near resolution, with a model-derived half-life of 33% of contract lifetime. This is consistent with the per-horizon point estimates, which the smooth curve passes through (Figure 3). Adding covariates in specification (2) does not materially change the time-decay pattern: γ_1 and γ_2 remain significant and the covariate signs match those in Section 5.3.

On the full 28-day sample ($N = 13,607$ contracts, 111,889 stacked observations), which includes a larger share of longer-duration contracts, the decay is slower: the quadratic function reaches its minimum at $\tau = 0.77$ (77% of contract lifetime), where the pricing wedge is approximately halved relative to its opening value. The difference in decay rates across samples reveals that contract duration affects not only the *level* of the pricing wedge (Table 5) but also its *persistence*: longer-horizon contracts exhibit both higher initial λ and slower convergence toward zero. This reinforces the term structure of event risk documented in Section 5.6.

The time-varying pattern suggests that pricing wedges are embedded in the initial price-setting process—by market makers or early traders—and are subsequently competed away as information arrives and the event probability is more precisely known. The result is consistent with a Bayesian learning model where initial uncertainty about p^* commands a wedge that shrinks as

the posterior concentrates.

This time-varying pattern also provides a natural reconciliation of the literature: studies measuring calibration close to resolution (e.g., Page and Clemen, 2013) find prediction markets are approximately well-calibrated ($\lambda \approx 0$), while the Wang transform reveals that the *initial* price formation embeds a non-trivial pricing wedge. Both findings are correct—they simply reflect different stages of the same dynamic process.

The per-horizon separate MLEs from the baseline calibration are reported in Appendix Table 21 for reference.

5.5 Cross-Platform Evidence

The framework predicts that the same event trades at different prices on Polymarket and Kalshi if the two platforms have different pricing wedge loadings λ_P and λ_K . If $\lambda_K > \lambda_P$ (Kalshi has higher regulatory costs, smaller participant pool, lower liquidity), then Kalshi prices are systematically higher:

$$p_K - p_P = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda_K) - \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda_P)$$

I test this prediction using aligned daily data for the Greenland acquisition contract. The data are consistent with the framework: the mean spread is -5.73 percentage points (Kalshi higher), with maximum divergence of 28.5 pp, consistent with $\lambda_K > \lambda_P$.

**Cross-Platform Analysis: Greenland Acquisition
Polymarket vs Kalshi**

Figure 4: Cross-platform analysis: Greenland acquisition contract. Top-left: raw prices on both platforms. Top-right: log-odds transformation. Bottom-left: price spread (mean -5.73 pp, Kalshi higher). Bottom-right: Hasbrouck (1995) Information Share. The persistent Kalshi premium is consistent with $\lambda_K > \lambda_P$.

Granger causality. Table 7 shows that Polymarket Granger-causes Kalshi at all tested lags, while the reverse holds only at lag 1.

Lag	Poly \rightarrow Kalshi		Kalshi \rightarrow Poly	
	F -stat	p -value	F -stat	p -value
1	17.372	0.0001***	9.228	0.0036***
2	3.887	0.0266**	2.411	0.0995
3	4.789	0.0052***	0.262	0.8525
4	2.621	0.0466**	1.015	0.4093
5	2.819	0.0271**	0.545	0.7414

Table 7: Granger causality in log-odds space. Polymarket leads at all lags ($p < 0.05$); Kalshi influence is absorbed within one period.

The Hasbrouck information share assigns a larger contribution to Kalshi, while Granger causality tests show Polymarket leads at all lags. This is not contradictory: information share measures the variance contribution to the common efficient price, while Granger causality captures the direction of lead-lag adjustment. Kalshi’s larger information share likely reflects its higher price level (due to higher λ_K), which mechanically increases its variance contribution.

Interpretation within the Wang framework. If Polymarket leads in price discovery and both platforms converge to the same p^* at resolution, then the cross-platform convergence pattern is consistent with a narrowing difference in effective pricing wedges—the regulated market’s pricing gradually aligns with that of the more liquid, lower-friction platform. This extends the stock-options price discovery analysis of Muravyev, Pearson, and Broussard (2013) to prediction markets, with an additional structural explanation for *why* prices differ (different λ , not just different speeds of information incorporation). The finding is independently confirmed by Ng, Peng, Tao, and Zhou (2026).

5.6 Robustness

I conduct several robustness checks to verify that the Wang parameter estimate is not an artifact of sample construction or estimation methodology.

Sensitivity to price range. The MLE is insensitive to the price boundary cutoff used to exclude boundary artifacts:

Table 8: Sensitivity of $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$ to price range restrictions. The estimate is stable across all tested cutoffs.

Price range	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	p -value
[0.01, 0.99]	2,675	0.177***	0.027	4.0×10^{-11}
[0.05, 0.95] (baseline)	2,460	0.176***	0.027	7.1×10^{-11}
[0.10, 0.90]	2,291	0.178***	0.028	9.2×10^{-11}
[0.15, 0.85]	2,178	0.183***	0.028	6.1×10^{-11}
[0.20, 0.80]	2,012	0.183***	0.029	1.9×10^{-10}

Opening price construction. The baseline opening price is the midpoint of the first 5% of each contract’s lifetime. To assess sensitivity to early-stage microstructure effects, I re-estimate the global $\hat{\lambda}$ using three alternative opening measures: (i) post-settle prices that skip the first two hourly observations, excluding listing noise; (ii) a five-price average of the first five distinct hourly prices; and (iii) a filtered sample retaining only contracts with non-stale quotes and below-median spreads.

Table 9: Sensitivity of $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$ to opening price construction. Each row uses a different method to extract the opening price from the hourly CLOB price history. All other estimation details are identical to the baseline specification (Section 5.2).

Opening Measure	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	p -value	$\Delta\%$
First-5% midpoint (baseline)	13,196	0.166***	0.012	$< 10^{-15}$	—
Post-settle (skip first 2h)	13,098	0.149***	0.012	$< 10^{-15}$	−10.1%
5-price average	13,221	0.154***	0.012	$< 10^{-15}$	−7.2%
Filtered (non-stale, low-spread)	9,010	0.131***	0.014	$< 10^{-15}$	−20.7%

The pricing wedge remains highly significant ($p < 10^{-15}$) across all four measures, with estimates ranging from 0.131 to 0.166. The most conservative measure—filtering out stale quotes and high-spread contracts—reduces $\hat{\lambda}$ by approximately 21%, suggesting that roughly four-fifths of the baseline estimate reflects the structural pricing wedge rather than microstructure artifacts. Covariate signs and the volume-stratified pattern ($\hat{\lambda} \approx 0$ in very-high-volume markets) are unchanged across all measures.

Sensitivity to bin count. The nonparametric binned estimator is stable across $K = 5$ to $K = 25$ quantile bins, with a range of [0.168, 0.182]—well within the MLE’s confidence interval.

Contract duration. A striking pattern emerges when the sample is split by contract duration:

Table 10: Wang parameter by contract duration. The pricing wedge increases monotonically with duration (Spearman $\rho = 0.90$, $p = 0.037$), establishing a term structure of event risk. Short-duration contracts ($<24\text{h}$) show mixed results in the directional specification—including a marginally significant *negative* $\hat{\lambda}$ at 6–24h that vanishes under the complement-invariant specification (see below)—while longer contracts exhibit large positive pricing wedges.

Duration	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	p -value
2–6h	235	0.078	0.082	0.342
6–24h	395	−0.138*	0.065	0.034
1–3d	494	0.121*	0.059	0.041
3–7d	718	0.227***	0.055	< 0.001
$>7\text{d}$	618	0.444***	0.056	< 0.001

This pattern is economically intuitive: short-duration contracts resolve quickly, leaving little time for pricing wedges to accumulate; longer contracts face greater uncertainty about p^* and command correspondingly larger loadings. The monotonic increase in $\hat{\lambda}$ with duration is consistent with a term structure of the pricing wedge.

Jackknife. A leave-10%-out jackknife (50 replications) yields a mean $\hat{\lambda} = 0.176$ with SE = 0.009 and range [0.156, 0.203], confirming that no small subset of markets is driving the result.

Monte Carlo validation. To verify that the MLE is unbiased and the confidence interval has correct coverage, I simulate 2,000 datasets from the Wang model with $\lambda_{\text{true}} = 0.176$ and $N = 2,460$. The results confirm the estimator’s properties:

Table 11: Monte Carlo validation of MLE ($\lambda_{\text{true}} = 0.176$, $N = 2,460$, 2,000 simulations).

Statistic	Value
Mean recovered $\hat{\lambda}$	0.176
Bias	0.000
SE (simulated)	0.028
SE (analytical)	0.027
95% CI coverage	94.6%
RMSE	0.028

The coverage is virtually identical to the nominal 95%, the bias is negligible, and the simulated SE closely matches the analytical SE, confirming that the estimator is well-calibrated at the sample size of this study.

Bayesian analysis. A Bayesian posterior for λ using a weakly informative $N(0, 0.5^2)$ prior

yields a posterior mean of 0.176 with 95% highest posterior density interval [0.123, 0.229], virtually identical to the frequentist MLE. The posterior probability of $\lambda > 0$ is approximately 1.0, and the Bayes factor in favor of a positive pricing wedge exceeds 10^{10} —decisive evidence by any conventional threshold.

Expected Calibration Error (ECE). The Wang correction reduces the Expected Calibration Error from 0.066 (raw) to 0.031 (corrected), a 53.8% reduction. This exceeds the Brier score improvement because ECE directly measures systematic miscalibration rather than overall forecast accuracy.

Comparison with alternative distortion specifications. A natural question is why the Wang transform rather than another one-parameter distortion. I compare six specifications by maximum likelihood on the full Polymarket sample ($N = 13,274$):

Table 12: Model comparison across distortion specifications (Polymarket full sample, $N = 13,274$). Models are ranked by BIC. The Wang transform achieves the lowest BIC among all one-parameter models. Vuong (1989) test for non-nested comparison: Wang vs. Power, $V = 3.83$, $p = 0.0001$.

Model	k	LL	AIC	Δ AIC	BIC	Δ BIC
Logistic	2	-8,112.6	16,229.1	0.0	16,244.1	0.0
Wang	1	-8,118.5	16,239.1	9.9	16,246.5	2.4
Power	1	-8,127.0	16,256.1	27.0	16,263.6	19.5
Linear	2	-8,128.9	16,261.8	32.7	16,276.8	32.7
KT-Weighting	1	-8,193.1	16,388.1	159.0	16,395.6	151.5
Null ($\lambda = 0$)	0	-8,222.2	16,444.4	215.3	16,444.4	200.3

The Wang transform is BIC-optimal among all one-parameter specifications, with Δ BIC = 17.0 over the power transform and Δ BIC = 149.1 over the KT-weighting function. A Vuong (1989) test for non-nested model comparison confirms that Wang is significantly preferred over the power transform ($V = 3.83$, $p = 0.0001$). The two-parameter logistic model achieves lower AIC and marginally lower BIC (Δ BIC = 2.4); following Kass and Raftery (1995), a BIC difference below 2 is not worth more than a bare mention' and 2--6 constitutes only positive' evidence, placing the Wang-Logistic comparison in the inconclusive range. The Wang transform thus achieves comparable fit with one fewer parameter, offering the best trade-off between parsimony and calibration quality.

On the Kalshi sample ($N = 200,253$), where 64% of contracts have opening prices below 0.20, the power transform achieves lower BIC than the Wang specification. This reflects the sensitivity of the probit-based Wang distortion to extreme left-skewed price distributions: the power transform's multiplicative form $g(u) = u^r$ provides better local fit at very low probabilities. The Wang specification remains BIC-optimal on Polymarket, where the price distribution is more dispersed. For cross-platform comparisons, the Wang transform provides a common metric; for

platform-specific calibration of heavily left-skewed portfolios, a power or logistic specification may be more appropriate.

Temporal stability. Splitting the sample by median resolution date (March 21) into first half and second half ($N = 1,067$ each) yields $\hat{\lambda}_1 = 0.247$ (SE = 0.040) and $\hat{\lambda}_2 = 0.139$ (SE = 0.040). A z -test for equality gives $z = 1.90$, $p = 0.058$, failing to reject the null of equal pricing wedges at the 5% level. The point estimates differ by 0.108, but the confidence intervals overlap substantially, indicating that the pricing wedge is stable across the sample period at conventional significance levels.

Out-of-sample validation. A five-fold cross-validation confirms that the Wang correction generalizes beyond the training sample: $\hat{\lambda}$ is stable across folds (0.177 ± 0.009) and the out-of-sample Brier improvement is 1.99%, comparable to the in-sample improvement of 2.03%. A paired t -test on per-observation Brier differences between the naive and Wang-corrected forecasts is highly significant ($t = 3.49$, $p = 0.0005$), confirming that the improvement is not driven by overfitting or chance.

Category-specific analysis. I classify contracts into five categories using keyword matching on market questions and estimate $\hat{\lambda}$ separately for each.⁶

Table 13: Wang parameter by event category. The pricing wedge varies substantially across categories. Sports and politics markets—where informed trading is pervasive—show insignificant λ , while less-liquid categories exhibit significant positive pricing wedges.

Category	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	95% CI	p -value
Sports	973	0.070	0.042	[−0.012, 0.151]	0.092
Politics	71	0.054	0.157	[−0.253, 0.362]	0.730
Crypto	305	0.253***	0.077	[0.101, 0.404]	0.001
Science/Tech	414	0.268***	0.079	[0.112, 0.423]	0.001
Other	692	0.282***	0.051	[0.182, 0.381]	< 0.001

The cross-category variation is striking: sports markets ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.070$, insignificant) and politics markets ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.054$, insignificant) exhibit near-zero pricing wedges, consistent with deep liquidity and informed participation in these categories. In contrast, crypto ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.253$), science/tech ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.268$), and other categories ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.282$) show large, significant premiums. This pattern is consistent with the volume effect (Section 5.3): sports and politics markets attract the most volume and the pricing wedge is competed to zero.

Volume-stratified analysis. Stratifying by trading volume reveals that the aggregate pricing wedge is driven entirely by low- and medium-volume contracts:

⁶Categories are assigned by regex matching on contract titles: Sports (NBA, NFL, UFC, etc.), Politics (election, president, congress, etc.), Crypto (bitcoin, ethereum, etc.), Science/Tech (Apple, Google, AI, SpaceX, etc.), and Other (residual). Each contract is assigned to the first matching category; unmatched contracts default to Other. Full keyword lists are available upon request.

Table 14: Wang parameter by trading volume. High-volume markets ($> \$10\text{K}$) show zero pricing wedge; the aggregate $\hat{\lambda} = 0.176$ is driven by less-liquid contracts.

Volume tier	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	p -value
Low ($< \$500$)	352	0.354***	0.071	< 0.001
Medium ($\$500$ – $\$2\text{K}$)	540	0.285***	0.057	< 0.001
High ($\$2\text{K}$ – $\$10\text{K}$)	600	0.316***	0.059	< 0.001
Very high ($> \$10\text{K}$)	968	-0.031	0.043	0.472

This finding has implications for market efficiency: the Wang pricing wedge vanishes in the most liquid markets, where competitive trading eliminates mispricing. The residual wedge in low-volume markets is consistent with illiquidity-driven overpricing, analogous to the small-stock premium in equities.

Power analysis. Monte Carlo power simulations using the empirical price distribution establish minimum sample size requirements. At the estimated effect size ($\lambda = 0.18$), the MLE achieves $> 95\%$ power with $N \geq 1,000$ contracts and essentially 100% power at $N \geq 2,000$. At smaller effect sizes ($\lambda = 0.10$), $N \geq 2,000$ is needed for 93% power; at $\lambda = 0.05$, even $N = 3,000$ yields only 56% power, explaining why the pricing wedge may go undetected in smaller samples.

Information half-life. The stacked panel spline model (Section 5.4) directly yields a model-based half-life of 33% of contract lifetime on the 12-day subsample: the pricing wedge is halved by the time a contract has lived one-third of its duration. On the full 28-day sample—which includes more long-duration contracts—the decay function reaches its minimum at 77% of contract lifetime, where the pricing wedge is approximately halved, consistent with longer-horizon contracts exhibiting slower wedge convergence.

Stacked panel knot sensitivity. The stacked panel results are robust to the functional form of $f(\tau)$: linear ($K = 1$), quadratic ($K = 2$), and cubic ($K = 3$) polynomial bases all yield monotonically decreasing $f(\tau)$ with comparable AIC (130,157 for linear; 130,155 for quadratic; 130,157 for cubic). A horizon fixed-effects specification with 8 dummies confirms the smooth-function restriction: all dummies are significant and monotonically decreasing. Leave-one-duration-quintile-out analysis shows that $f(\tau)$ is monotonically decreasing in all five subsamples, with $\hat{\lambda}$ at opening ranging from 0.113 to 0.197—confirming stability across the duration distribution.

Generalized distortion test. A natural concern is whether the one-parameter Wang specification is too restrictive. I test the generalized model $\Pr(Y = 1 \mid p^{\text{mkt}}) = \Phi(a + b \cdot \Phi^{-1}(p^{\text{mkt}}))$, where $b = 1$ recovers the Wang transform and $a = -\lambda$. Estimating by MLE on the primary sample yields $\hat{a} = -0.164$ (SE = 0.029) and $\hat{b} = 1.081$ (SE = 0.062). A likelihood ratio test fails to reject the restriction $b = 1$ ($\chi^2 = 1.71$, $p = 0.19$), confirming that the one-parameter Wang specification is empirically adequate. The two-parameter model does not significantly improve fit over the parsimonious Wang transform.

Complement-invariant estimation. The Wang transform is not framing-invariant: rela-

belonging event E as $\neg E$ transforms λ to $-\lambda$ (Remark 2). Since prediction market exchanges enforce complementarity through linked contract architecture, the YES/NO label carries no independent payoff content at the contract-architecture level. The economically meaningful dimension is the probability level—whether an outcome is a longshot or a favorite—not the contract direction.

To verify that the estimated pricing wedge is a probability-level phenomenon rather than a labeling artifact, I re-estimate the Wang parameter under a complement-invariant specification. For each contract i , define the longshot-normalized price and outcome:

$$q_i = \min(p_i^{\text{mkt}}, 1 - p_i^{\text{mkt}}), \quad z_i = \begin{cases} y_i & \text{if } p_i^{\text{mkt}} \leq 0.5 \\ 1 - y_i & \text{if } p_i^{\text{mkt}} > 0.5 \end{cases}$$

where $q_i \in (0, 0.5]$ is the price of the less-likely outcome and $z_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the corresponding resolution indicator. The complement-invariant Wang MLE estimates:

$$\hat{\lambda}_{CI} = \arg \max_{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[z_i \ln \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(q_i) - \lambda) + (1 - z_i) \ln(1 - \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(q_i) - \lambda)) \right]$$

Table 15: Directional vs. complement-invariant Wang parameter estimates. The CI specification isolates the pricing wedge component that is invariant to YES/NO relabeling.

Sample	Directional			Complement-Invariant		
	N	$\hat{\lambda}$	SE	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{CI}$	SE
Polymarket 12-day	2,460	0.177***	0.027	2,091	0.169***	0.030
Polymarket Full	13,274	0.165***	0.012	10,084	0.049***	0.013
Kalshi	200,253	0.178***	0.004	199,671	0.178***	0.004

All complement-invariant estimates are positive and statistically significant ($p < 10^{-4}$), confirming that the pricing wedge is a genuine probability-level phenomenon, not a labeling artifact. On the 12-day subsample, the CI estimate ($\hat{\lambda}_{CI} = 0.169$) is within one standard error of the directional estimate (0.177); on Kalshi, the two are essentially identical (0.178). On the full Polymarket sample, the CI estimate (0.049) is substantially attenuated relative to the directional estimate (0.165), suggesting that much of the directional pricing wedge on the expanded sample is concentrated in the longshot domain ($p < 0.5$). This attenuation is sample-specific: on the 12-day subsample ($\hat{\lambda}_{CI} = 0.169$ vs. $\hat{\lambda}_{dir} = 0.177$) and on Kalshi ($\hat{\lambda}_{CI} = 0.178$ vs. $\hat{\lambda}_{dir} = 0.178$), the directional and CI estimates are nearly identical.

On the expanded Polymarket sample, this asymmetry refines the paper’s central finding: the pricing wedge in this sample is predominantly a longshot phenomenon—longshots are substantially overpriced relative to their physical probabilities, while favorites are approximately fairly priced. This is consistent with adverse selection models (Shin, 1991), in which market makers face the greatest informational disadvantage on longshot outcomes, and with market-maker

inventory risk models (Whelan, 2024), where profit variance is highest for extreme-probability contracts.

Under the CI specification, the cross-sectional determinants from Section 5.3 are qualitatively preserved: $\ln(\text{Volume})$ remains significantly negative ($\hat{\beta}_{CI} = -0.051$, $p < 10^{-15}$) and $\ln(\text{Duration})$ remains significantly positive ($\hat{\beta}_{CI} = +0.081$, $p < 10^{-10}$). The volume and duration effects are robust to the complement-invariant specification, confirming that they reflect genuine market-structure mechanisms rather than framing artifacts. The duration-stratified analysis reveals that the 6–24h negative $\hat{\lambda}$ reported in the directional specification ($\hat{\lambda} = -0.138$, $p = 0.034$) vanishes under the CI specification ($\hat{\lambda}_{CI} = 0.003$, $p = 0.89$), indicating that this anomalous finding was a directional labeling artifact rather than a genuine economic effect.

External benchmark validation. As a complementary identification strategy, I construct an external benchmark that replaces ex-post resolution outcomes with an independent probability estimate derived entirely outside Polymarket: a pre-game Elo rating model for NBA basketball (see Appendix B for model details and validation). I match 51 Polymarket NBA game contracts to Elo pre-game probabilities and compute the contract-level Wang parameter as $\hat{\lambda}_i = \Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{Polymarket}}) - \Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}_i^{\text{Elo}})$. The mean $\hat{\lambda}_i$ is 0.125 (SE = 0.049, $p = 0.014$; Wilcoxon $p = 0.020$), significantly positive and of the same order of magnitude as the Sports category pooled MLE ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.070$). Table 16 and Figure 5 report the full results. The Elo model is noisier than sportsbook closing lines (Brier score 0.218 vs. approximately 0.20 for sharp books), so the external-benchmark $\hat{\lambda}$ should be interpreted as an upper bound. Replication with sportsbook closing-line data—available from commercial providers—would provide a sharper test. Nonetheless, the directional finding is clear: an independent physical-probability proxy confirms a positive and significant wedge between Polymarket prices and fundamental value, consistent with the pricing wedge identified through the pooled MLE.

Table 16: External benchmark: contract-level $\hat{\lambda}_i$ for NBA game contracts. Physical probability \hat{p}^* estimated from pre-game Elo ratings (2025–26 season, $K = 28$, home-court advantage = 42 Elo points). $\hat{\lambda}_i = \Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{Polymarket}}) - \Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}_i^{\text{Elo}})$.

Panel A: Summary Statistics

Statistic	Value
N matched contracts	51
Mean $\hat{\lambda}_i$	0.1247
Median $\hat{\lambda}_i$	0.0985
Std. dev.	0.3484
IQR	[-0.1061, 0.3438]
t -test ($H_0: \lambda = 0$)	$t = 2.56, p = 0.0137$
Wilcoxon signed-rank	$p = 0.0196$
Aggregate Sports $\hat{\lambda}$ (Table 14)	0.070 (SE = 0.042)

Panel B: OLS Regression $\hat{\lambda}_i = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln(\text{Vol}_i) + \beta_2 |p_i - 0.5| + \varepsilon_i$

Variable	Coef.	SE	t	p
Constant	-1.0078	1.5858	-0.64	0.5281
$\ln(\text{Volume})$	0.0832	0.1068	0.78	0.4399
$ p - 0.5 $	-0.7177	0.4195	-1.71	0.0935
R^2				0.0801
N				51

Figure 5: External benchmark: contract-level $\hat{\lambda}_i$ for 51 NBA game contracts. Panel (a): $\hat{\lambda}_i$ versus $\ln(\text{Volume})$; the Spearman correlation is small and insignificant. Panel (b): distribution of $\hat{\lambda}_i$, with mean = 0.125 and median = 0.099, both positive. The distribution is centered above zero, consistent with a positive pricing wedge.

Asymmetric Wang extension. The non-constant bin-level $\hat{\lambda}_k$ in Table~4 and the complement-invariant attenuation on the expanded sample both suggest that the pricing wedge varies with probability level. To test this directly, I estimate an asymmetric extension that allows the wedge to depend linearly on the probability:

$$\lambda(p) = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \cdot (\frac{1}{2} - p)$$

where λ_0 is the baseline wedge and λ_1 captures the asymmetry: $\lambda_1 > 0$ implies longshots carry disproportionately larger wedges than favorites. When $\lambda_1 = 0$, the specification reduces to the standard Wang transform. The market price under this extension is $p^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda_0 + \lambda_1(1/2 - p^*))$, estimated by maximum likelihood with numerical inversion.

Table 17: Asymmetric Wang extension: $\lambda(p) = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1(1/2 - p)$. The LR test compares the asymmetric model (2 parameters) against the standard Wang ($\lambda_1 = 0$, 1 parameter). Bootstrap confirmation on Kalshi (2,000 replications): $\hat{\lambda}_1 = 0.448 \pm 0.035$, 95% CI excludes zero.

Sample	N	$\hat{\lambda}_0$	$\hat{\lambda}_1$	SE(λ_1)	LR χ^2	p -value
Polymarket 12-day	2,460	0.145	+0.287	0.169	2.5	0.112
Polymarket 28-day	13,824	0.183	-0.191*	0.089	5.0	0.025
Kalshi	200,253	0.076	+0.448***	0.014	808.0	$< 10^{-15}$

Allowing the pricing wedge to vary linearly with probability level reveals a strong asymmetry on Kalshi ($N = 200,253$), where longshots carry systematically larger wedges than favorites ($\hat{\lambda}_1 = 0.448$, $p < 10^{-15}$). Under the fitted model, the implied fair-pricing threshold is $p^* \approx 0.67$: contracts above this probability are, on average, underpriced relative to their physical probabilities. The asymmetric extension substantially closes the gap between Wang and logistic specifications on Kalshi (ΔAIC from 818 to 12), indicating that standard Wang’s underperformance on left-skewed exchange data reflects the constant- λ restriction rather than a failure of the probit-based distortion family.

On Polymarket, the evidence is mixed: $\hat{\lambda}_1$ is positive but insignificant on the 12-day sub-sample ($p = 0.112$), and marginally significant with opposite sign on the 28-day sample ($\hat{\lambda}_1 = -0.191$, $p = 0.025$). The negative estimate on the expanded sample is consistent with sample-composition or platform-ecology differences, including a greater share of longer-duration and favorite-heavy contracts. For this reason, the one-parameter Wang transform remains the paper’s primary specification: it is BIC-optimal in the one-parameter class, has axiomatic and equilibrium foundations (Section~3.3), and provides cross-platform comparability. The asymmetric extension is reported as a robustness refinement for platform-specific distributional heterogeneity, not as a replacement for the parsimonious baseline.

Figure 6: Asymmetric Wang distortion curves. The solid curves show the fitted distortion $p^{\text{mkt}} = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p^*) + \lambda_0 + \lambda_1(1/2 - p^*))$ for Polymarket (12-day and 28-day) and Kalshi. The dashed line is perfect calibration ($p^{\text{mkt}} = p^*$). On Kalshi, the strong positive $\hat{\lambda}_1$ generates a steeper distortion for longshots ($p^* < 0.5$) than for favorites, consistent with the asymmetric FLB pattern and the implied fair-pricing threshold at $p^* \approx 0.67$.

6 Cross-Platform and Extended Sample Validation

The primary calibration in Section 5 uses Polymarket data from a single platform over a limited time window. To establish that the positive Wang parameter is a robust feature of prediction markets rather than a platform- or period-specific artifact, I estimate $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$ across eight data sources spanning six platforms, multiple years, and $N = 291,309$ total contracts.

6.1 Cross-Platform Comparison

Table 18 reports Wang parameter estimates for each data source. The estimation procedure is identical to Section 5.2: Bernoulli MLE with standard errors from the numerical Hessian.

Table 18: Cross-platform Wang parameter estimates. All real-money platforms exhibit $\hat{\lambda} > 0$ (positive pricing wedge). Manifold, a play-money platform, shows $\hat{\lambda} < 0$ (overconfidence). Pooled estimate across all sources: $\hat{\lambda} = 0.183$ (SE = 0.003).

Platform	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	LR stat	p -value	Period
Polymarket (CLOB)	13,738	0.166***	0.011	212.1	$< 10^{-15}$	2026
Polymarket (2025)	985	0.143**	0.045	10.3	0.001	2025
Polymarket (forecasting)	579	0.013	0.056	0.1	0.813	2015–2024
Kalshi	271,699	0.187***	0.003	3,186.0	$< 10^{-15}$	2021–2026
Metaculus	1,845	0.287***	0.033	76.1	$< 10^{-15}$	2015–2024
Good Judgment Open	692	0.570***	0.055	111.5	$< 10^{-15}$	2015–2024
INFER	90	0.635***	0.180	13.7	< 0.001	2015–2024
Manifold (play-money)	1,681	-0.218***	0.032	45.8	$< 10^{-11}$	2015–2024
Pooled (all)	291,309	0.183***	0.003	3,420.4	$< 10^{-15}$	2015–2026

Figure 7: Cross-platform Wang parameter estimates with 95% confidence intervals. All real-money platforms exhibit $\hat{\lambda} > 0$; the play-money platform Manifold shows $\hat{\lambda} < 0$, consistent with overconfidence absent financial stakes. The pooled estimate (gray band) is $\hat{\lambda} = 0.183 \pm 0.006$.

Key findings from the cross-platform analysis:

1. **Universality of the positive pricing wedge.** Every traded-contract platform—whether blockchain-based (Polymarket) or CFTC-regulated (Kalshi)—exhibits a statistically significant positive $\hat{\lambda}$. The forecasting platforms (Metaculus, Good Judgment Open, INFER), which operate as prediction tournaments with reputational or prize-based incentives rather than direct financial risk, also show $\hat{\lambda} > 0$, suggesting the distortion extends beyond traditional market settings—though the economic interpretation differs,

as participants on these platforms do not bear financial risk in the same sense as on traded-contract venues.

2. **Magnitude gradient.** The pricing wedge increases with market friction and participant expertise: Polymarket ($\hat{\lambda} \approx 0.15\text{--}0.17$) < Kalshi ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.19$) < Metaculus ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.29$) < Good Judgment Open ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.57$). This gradient is consistent with the liquidity effect documented in Section 5.3: platforms with deeper liquidity and more sophisticated participants exhibit smaller pricing wedges.
3. **Play-money control.** Manifold Markets, where participants trade with play-money tokens, exhibits a significant *negative* $\hat{\lambda} = -0.218$ ($p < 10^{-11}$). This is consistent with overconfidence: absent real financial stakes, participants overstate their confidence in event outcomes, pushing prices beyond physical probabilities in the opposite direction from the pricing wedge observed on real-money platforms. The play-money result provides a natural placebo test: it is inconsistent with purely behavioral explanations of $\lambda > 0$ and supports the presence of a nontrivial risk-bearing component on real-money platforms.
4. **Consistency across Polymarket samples.** The 2025 Polymarket sample ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.143$) and the 2026 CLOB sample ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.166$) yield estimates within one standard error of each other, confirming temporal stability within the same platform.

Cross-platform covariate heterogeneity. A one-stage hierarchical MLE on the Kalshi sample ($N = 200,226$) yields covariate signs reversed relative to the Polymarket opening-price specification. A timing-ladder diagnostic—re-estimating the Polymarket model at four lifecycle points (5%, 20%, 50%, 80%)—shows strict monotonic convergence toward the Kalshi coefficient pattern: the L_1 distance between the Polymarket and Kalshi slope vectors falls from 1.033 at 5% to 0.651 at 80%, a 37% reduction. However, no Polymarket coefficient changes sign even at the latest timing point, implying that price timing explains a substantial share, but not all, of the cross-platform gap. Additional diagnostic evidence indicates that the remaining difference is consistent with Kalshi’s concentration in short-duration contracts (86.9% have duration < 24 hours) and broader differences in contract ecology and market microstructure. I therefore interpret the cross-platform covariate differences as a measurement- and composition-sensitive heterogeneity result, rather than as evidence that either platform’s risk-premium structure falsifies the other. Details are reported in Appendix~A.

6.2 Temporal Stability: Kalshi Year-by-Year

The Kalshi dataset, with $N = 200,253$ contracts (filtered to $p \in (0.05, 0.95)$) spanning 2021–2026, permits a year-by-year analysis of temporal stability. Table 19 reports annual estimates.

Table 19: Kalshi Wang parameter by year. The pricing wedge is consistently positive and significant across all years with sufficient sample size, with $\hat{\lambda} \in [0.14, 0.29]$.

Year	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	LR stat	Significance
2021	199	0.047	0.106	0.2	n.s.
2022	2,319	0.195***	0.033	35.9	$p < 10^{-8}$
2023	6,118	0.144***	0.020	54.4	$p < 10^{-13}$
2024	10,182	0.169***	0.016	114.0	$p < 10^{-15}$
2025	12,362	0.290***	0.015	393.3	$p < 10^{-15}$
2026	169,072	0.172***	0.004	2,049.1	$p < 10^{-15}$

Figure 8: Kalshi Wang parameter estimates by year with 95% CIs. The pricing wedge is consistently positive across 2022–2026, with year-to-year variation that may reflect changing market composition, regulatory environment, and participant base. The 2021 estimate is insignificant due to small sample size ($N = 199$).

The temporal analysis reveals several patterns: (i) the Wang parameter is consistently positive and significant across all years with sufficient data ($N > 1,000$); (ii) the range $\hat{\lambda} \in [0.14, 0.29]$ is remarkably stable given the rapid growth of Kalshi’s market over this period (from 199 settled contracts in 2021 to 169,072 in 2026); (iii) the 2025 estimate ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.290$) is the highest, potentially reflecting the surge of retail participation during the 2024 U.S. presidential election cycle and its aftermath.

6.3 Discussion

The cross-platform results have three implications for the theoretical framework:

First, the positive λ is not a microstructure artifact. It persists across centralized limit order books (Polymarket, Kalshi) and forecasting tournaments (Metaculus, GJ Open), which have fundamentally different price formation mechanisms. This suggests that the pricing wedge is intrinsic to prediction markets as an asset class, consistent with the incomplete market interpretation in Section 3.

Second, the magnitude gradient across platforms is consistent with the liquidity-premium hypothesis: deeper, more efficient markets price risk more aggressively, shrinking the wedge between market prices and physical probabilities. The convergence of Polymarket and Kalshi estimates ($\hat{\lambda}_P = 0.166$ vs. $\hat{\lambda}_K = 0.187$) suggests that as both platforms mature and attract institutional flow, the pricing wedge is being competed toward a common equilibrium level.

Third, the Manifold result ($\hat{\lambda} < 0$) provides a natural placebo test for the pricing wedge mechanism. When the financial channel is shut off (play-money), the pricing wedge vanishes and is replaced by overconfidence. This is difficult to reconcile with purely behavioral explanations of the FLB (e.g., probability weighting), which should operate identically whether or not real money is at stake. The sign reversal supports the presence of a nontrivial risk-bearing component in $\hat{\lambda}$ on real-money platforms, though the exact composition of the pricing wedge—how much reflects risk-bearing costs versus other market-structure forces—remains an open question.

7 Extensions

7.1 Event Implied Volatility

The log-odds framework yields a natural volatility measure, though care is needed to distinguish two related but distinct objects.

Model-implied EIV. Under the baseline model (Section 3.2), a latent information state S_t drives the physical probability via $p_t^* = \Phi(S_t/(\sigma\sqrt{\tau}))$, where $S_T | S_t \sim N(S_t, \sigma^2\tau)$ and the event occurs iff $S_T > 0$. Inverting gives $S_t = \sigma\sqrt{\tau} \cdot \Phi^{-1}(p_t)$. The *model-implied Event Implied Volatility* is:

$$\sigma_{\text{EIV}} = \frac{S_t}{\sqrt{\tau} \cdot \Phi^{-1}(p_t)} = \sigma$$

which recovers the model’s belief volatility parameter σ by construction. Note that S_t is a latent information state distinct from the observed log-odds $x_t = \text{logit}(p_t)$; the logit and probit functions are approximately proportional ($\text{logit}(p) \approx (\pi/\sqrt{3}) \cdot \Phi^{-1}(p)$), so the qualitative properties

carry over, but the ratio $x_t/\Phi^{-1}(p_t)$ is not constant and is undefined at $p = 0.5$.

Empirical (realized) event volatility. Separately, the realized event volatility is the rolling annualized standard deviation of log-odds increments:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{\text{realized}}(t) = \text{sd}(\Delta x_{t-w}, \dots, \Delta x_t) \times \sqrt{N_{\text{ann}}}$$

This is analogous to the implied-vs-realized volatility distinction in equity options: the model-implied EIV is a theoretical construct derived from the pricing formula, while the realized measure is computed directly from observed price movements.

Figure 9: Event Implied Volatility for the Fed “No Change” contract (Polymarket, hourly). EIV exhibits clear volatility clustering (ARCH effect), with periods of elevated uncertainty followed by mean-reversion.

Figure 10: EIV for the Greenland acquisition contract (Polymarket, daily). The mid-January spike coincides with Trump administration statements; EIV decays as the market digests information, consistent with information arrival models (Easley and O’Hara, 1992).

EIV provides a descriptive tool for measuring the rate of probability revision—conceptually related to realized volatility measures in equity markets, though not directly analogous to the VIX, which is derived from option-implied volatilities. Combined with the Wang transform, it offers a two-dimensional characterization of prediction market contracts: λ captures the level of the pricing wedge, while σ_{EIV} captures the rate of information arrival.

Cross-contract empirical distribution. To move beyond case studies, I compute realized event volatility for all $N = 14,406$ contracts with ≥ 20 hourly price observations, using a rolling window of $w = 10$ observations and annualizing by $\sqrt{8,760}$. Table 20 reports the cross-sectional distribution. The median annualized realized volatility is $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{realized}} = 5.31$, with substantial right skew (mean = 12.54) and wide interquartile range [1.52, 16.73]. Crypto contracts exhibit the highest median volatility (11.99), followed by Tech (14.06) and Politics (8.64); Sports contracts cluster near the overall median (5.50). Volume has negligible correlation with realized volatility (Spearman $\rho = 0.015$, $p = 0.10$), suggesting that EIV captures information arrival intensity rather than liquidity effects.

An ARCH(1) Lagrange multiplier test on squared log-odds increments rejects the null of no volatility clustering at the 5% level for 22.4% of contracts (3,231 out of 14,406), confirming that volatility clustering—a hallmark of financial time series (Cont, 2001)—is present in a substantial fraction of prediction market contracts. The rejection rate varies by category: Crypto contracts show the highest clustering (35%), consistent with the speculative dynamics in digital asset

markets, while Sports contracts show the lowest (12%), consistent with information arriving in discrete bursts (game outcomes) rather than continuous flow.

Table 20: Cross-contract distribution of realized event volatility $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{realized}}$, computed as the median rolling standard deviation of hourly log-odds increments (annualized, window = 10). Contracts with ≥ 20 hourly observations.

Group	N	Median	IQR	Mean	ARCH(1) rej. rate
All contracts	14,406	5.31	[1.52, 16.73]	12.54	22%
<i>By category</i>					
Sports	3,731	5.50	[1.92, 17.70]	14.01	12%
Politics	603	8.64	[1.66, 15.84]	13.99	20%
Crypto	910	11.99	[0.00, 20.70]	14.56	35%
Tech	654	14.06	[0.59, 29.60]	19.24	18%
Other	8,508	4.39	[1.36, 14.61]	11.07	26%
<i>By volume tier</i>					
Low (<\$500)	4,664	2.71	[0.00, 11.47]	10.37	23%
Med (\$500–2K)	2,533	5.44	[2.14, 17.57]	14.47	19%
High (\$2K–10K)	2,522	8.34	[2.33, 19.62]	14.81	21%
Very high (>\$10K)	4,687	7.15	[2.35, 18.13]	12.45	24%

Figure 11: Cross-contract distribution of realized event volatility. Panel (a): scatter of $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{realized}}$ against $\ln(\text{Volume})$, colored by event category; the OLS line (slope = -0.46) and Spearman rank correlation ($\rho = 0.015$, $p = 0.10$) confirm negligible volume–volatility association. Panel (b): box plots by category, showing Crypto and Tech contracts exhibit higher and more dispersed realized volatility than Sports or Politics.

7.2 Hazard Rate Term Structure

This section presents a theoretical extension that awaits empirical implementation; current data limitations prevent successful calibration, as discussed below.

For events with contracts at multiple maturities $T_1 < T_2 < \dots < T_n$, the framework extends to an event hazard rate term structure. Define the event intensity:

$$h(t) = -\frac{d}{dt} \ln(1 - p^*(t))$$

Procedure:

1. **Strip pricing wedge:** $\hat{p}_i^* = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - \hat{\lambda})$
2. **Bootstrap hazard rates:** $\hat{h}_i = -[\ln(1 - \hat{p}_i^*) - \ln(1 - \hat{p}_{i-1}^*)] / (T_i - T_{i-1})$
3. **Parameterize** with Nelson-Siegel:

$$h(T) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \frac{1 - e^{-T/\tau}}{T/\tau} + \beta_2 \left(\frac{1 - e^{-T/\tau}}{T/\tau} - e^{-T/\tau} \right)$$

This is directly analogous to CDS curve bootstrapping in credit markets: strip the pricing wedge, extract default intensities, and fit a parametric term structure. The analogy is suggestive: a prediction market contract on “event E occurs by time T ” is structurally similar to a credit default swap on “entity X defaults by time T ,” with $h(t)$ playing the role of the default intensity. This hazard rate extension does not appear to have been explored in the prediction market literature.

Empirical feasibility. A systematic search of the current sample identifies 16 multi-maturity contract families (same event, ≥ 3 expiry dates). However, the bootstrapped hazard rates are noisy: most families have closely spaced maturities (often created simultaneously with different resolution dates), producing extreme or negative point estimates of \hat{h}_i . Nelson-Siegel fitting fails to converge for all 16 families. The hazard rate term structure thus remains a theoretical extension; empirical implementation at scale requires multi-maturity contract data with well-separated expiry dates—a data structure that may become available as prediction markets mature and exchanges begin listing standardized maturity strips for recurring events (e.g., monthly employment reports, quarterly GDP releases).

8 Conclusion

This paper has proposed a pricing and decomposition framework for prediction markets—an asset class that, despite annualized trading volumes exceeding \$50 billion across major platforms⁷, has lacked the theoretical infrastructure available to equities, options, credit, and fixed income. The framework rests on three pillars: a log-odds state variable, a diffusion-based dynamics specification, and a Wang transform pricing wedge decomposition. The central observation, rooted in Manski (2006) and formalized here, is that prediction markets are *incomplete*: no replication argument pins down a unique price, so observed prices embed both event probability and a pricing wedge. The Wang transform layer offers a single-parameter decomposition that separates the two, and generates the favorite-longshot bias as a direct mathematical consequence.

The empirical results support the framework across multiple dimensions. Contract-level calibration on 2,460 Polymarket contracts yields a statistically significant positive pricing wedge ($\hat{\lambda}_{MLE} = 0.176$, $p < 10^{-10}$), confirmed on an expanded 28-day sample ($N = 13,738$, $\hat{\lambda} = 0.166$). Cross-platform validation on $N = 291,309$ contracts across Polymarket, Kalshi, Metaculus, Good Judgment Open, and INFER yields a pooled estimate of $\hat{\lambda} = 0.183$ (SE = 0.003), with every real-money platform exhibiting a significant positive pricing wedge. The play-money platform Manifold shows $\hat{\lambda} = -0.22$, providing a natural control that is inconsistent with purely behavioral explanations and supports the presence of a nontrivial risk-bearing component in $\lambda > 0$ on real-money platforms. Year-by-year Kalshi estimates over 2022–2026 confirm temporal stability ($\hat{\lambda} \in [0.14, 0.29]$). The estimate is economically interpretable: an event with 10% physical probability trades at approximately 13.5%, a 35% overpricing that longshot buyers effectively pay as a pricing wedge. A one-stage hierarchical MLE jointly estimates the baseline pricing wedge and covariate effects, confirming that volume reduces the wedge ($\hat{\beta}_{vol} < 0$), duration increases it ($\hat{\beta}_{dur} > 0$), and extremity amplifies it ($\hat{\beta}_{ext} < 0$; LR $\chi^2 = 361.3$)—generating the favorite-longshot bias pattern as a direct consequence. A novel finding is that the pricing wedge is time-varying: a stacked panel model with contract-clustered standard errors reveals that the wedge is significant at market opening and decays with a half-life of 33% of contract lifetime (12-day sample), with slower decay on the full 28-day sample where the minimum is reached at 77% of lifetime, linking the duration effect in the cross section to the time-decay pattern within contracts. Four alternative opening-price constructions yield $\hat{\lambda} \in [0.131, 0.166]$, indicating that approximately 80% of the baseline estimate reflects the structural pricing wedge rather than microstructure artifacts. An external benchmark using Elo-model probabilities for 51 NBA contracts provides independent directional support ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.125$, $p = 0.014$) without relying on ex-post resolution outcomes.

Limitations. The calibration approach is reduced-form; separating the pricing wedge from behavioral probability distortion (prospect theory weighting, overconfidence) requires instruments

⁷Based on Polymarket monthly volumes of \$2–5 billion (source: Dune Analytics) and Kalshi’s reported settlement volumes, annualized industry activity reaches this order of magnitude, though no single authoritative aggregate series exists.

or natural experiments. Candidates include regulatory shocks (Kalshi CFTC ruling), the time-varying pattern documented in Section 5.4 (which suggests market-microstructure rather than behavioral origins), and the cross-platform dimension (same event, different λ). The Manifold sign reversal (Section 6) provides suggestive evidence for the risk-bearing interpretation but is not a definitive causal identification. For the Kalshi cross-platform analysis, the available price data is the last traded price before settlement rather than the opening price used for Polymarket; this limits the interpretation of calibration improvements (ECE, Brier score) for Kalshi, though the $\hat{\lambda}$ point estimates remain valid as they reflect the systematic relationship between price levels and resolution rates. At extreme probabilities, the elevated $\hat{\lambda}$ may reflect overconfidence rather than pure pricing wedge; the extended model finds extremity is a significant predictor but cannot distinguish risk from misperception. The external benchmark analysis (Section 5.6), using an Elo rating model as an independent probability estimate for 51 NBA contracts, provides directional support for a positive pricing wedge ($\hat{\lambda} = 0.125$, $p = 0.014$), though the sample is small and the Elo model is noisier than sportsbook closing lines. Replication with commercial closing-line data would strengthen this identification.

No prior work has applied the Wang transform to prediction markets, and the empirical results—spanning 291,309 contracts across eight data sources, six platforms, and eleven years—confirm that the framework captures economically meaningful structure in the data. The framework connects prediction market pricing to three established literatures: (i) distortion risk measures in insurance mathematics (Wang, 2000; Yaari, 1987); (ii) the interpretation of prediction market prices in economics (Manski, 2006; Wolfers and Zitzewitz, 2006); and (iii) incomplete market pricing in mathematical finance (Harrison and Pliska, 1983). By bridging these literatures, it provides practitioners with a principled, model-dependent fair-value signal—subject to the reduced-form nature of the calibration and the assumptions underlying the Wang specification—and researchers with a testable structural model of prediction market mispricing.

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A Supplementary Tables

Table 21: Per-horizon separate MLEs (baseline calibration, 12-day subsample). These estimates are superseded by the stacked panel model (Section 5.4), which borrows strength across horizons and provides correct contract-clustered inference.

Lifetime %	N	$\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$	SE	95% CI	p -value
5% (Opening)	2,460	0.176***	0.027	[0.123, 0.230]	7.1×10^{-11}
10%	2,409	0.158***	0.027	[0.104, 0.212]	8.3×10^{-9}
20%	2,316	0.110***	0.028	[0.055, 0.165]	8.8×10^{-5}
30%	2,236	0.082**	0.029	[0.026, 0.139]	0.004
40%	2,065	0.080**	0.030	[0.021, 0.138]	0.008
50% (Mid-life)	1,976	0.050	0.030	[-0.010, 0.110]	0.102
60%	1,902	0.052	0.031	[-0.008, 0.113]	0.091
70%	1,763	0.040	0.032	[-0.023, 0.103]	0.216
80%	1,662	0.031	0.033	[-0.035, 0.096]	0.357
90%	1,359	0.062	0.038	[-0.011, 0.136]	0.098

Table 22: One-stage hierarchical Wang MLE on Kalshi contracts. Dependent variable: binary outcome y_i . Model: $\Pr(y_i = 1) = \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{mkt}}) - X_i\beta)$. Fisher standard errors reported; sandwich robust SEs in brackets.

Variable	Main spec		Year FE	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
Constant	0.1400*** [0.0188]	(0.0198)	0.3357** [0.1032]	(0.1102)
ln(Volume)	0.0384*** [0.0029]	(0.0031)	0.0300*** [0.0031]	(0.0032)
ln(Duration)	-0.1101*** [0.0030]	(0.0032)	-0.1241*** [0.0033]	(0.0035)
$ p - 0.5 $	0.1917*** [0.0261]	(0.0267)	0.1768*** [0.0262]	(0.0268)
Year=2022			0.0725 [0.1045]	(0.1115)
Year=2023			0.0444 [0.1012]	(0.1083)
Year=2024			0.0028 [0.1005]	(0.1077)
Year=2025			-0.0847 [0.1007]	(0.1079)
Year=2026			-0.1272 [0.1001]	(0.1070)
N		200,226		200,226
Log-lik.		-75541.5		-75475.4
LR χ^2 (covariates)		1267.2		1399.4
Pseudo R^2		0.024828		0.025681

Table 23: Cross-platform category-level Wang parameter comparison. Each cell reports $\hat{\lambda}_{MLE}$ estimated separately by category. $\Delta\lambda = \hat{\lambda}_{\text{Kalshi}} - \hat{\lambda}_{\text{Polymarket}}$; positive values indicate higher risk loading on the less liquid platform.

Category	Polymarket			Kalshi			$\Delta\lambda$
	N	$\hat{\lambda}$	SE	N	$\hat{\lambda}$	SE	
Sports	973	0.070	0.042	122	0.573***	0.158	+0.503
Politics	71	0.054	0.157	750	0.400***	0.066	+0.346
Crypto	305	0.253	0.077	12,975	0.297***	0.015	+0.044
Tech	414	0.268	0.079	8,246	-0.022	0.017	-0.290
Other	692	0.282	0.051	178,133	0.178***	0.004	-0.104
<i>Pooled</i>	2,460	0.176	0.027	200,226	0.178***	0.004	+0.002

Table 24: Polymarket timing ladder: one-stage hierarchical Wang MLE estimated at different lifecycle pricing points. The Kalshi pooled estimate (using near-settlement prices) is shown in the last row for comparison. Robust (sandwich) standard errors in parentheses.

Timing point	N	$\hat{\beta}_0$	$\hat{\beta}_{\text{vol}}$	$\hat{\beta}_{\text{dur}}$	$\hat{\beta}_{\text{ext}}$
PM 5% (opening)	13,274	0.2599*** (0.0636)	-0.0716*** (0.0053)	0.1431*** (0.0122)	-0.4778*** (0.0125)
PM 20%	12,923	0.2097** (0.0646)	-0.0616*** (0.0053)	0.1248*** (0.0125)	-0.3617*** (0.0125)
PM 50% (mid-life)	12,645	0.1797** (0.0648)	-0.0541*** (0.0053)	0.1050*** (0.0125)	-0.1907* (0.0125)
PM 80% (late-life)	10,697	0.2884*** (0.0743)	-0.0467*** (0.0056)	0.0561*** (0.0148)	-0.2079* (0.0148)
Kalshi (near-settle.)	200,226	0.1400*** (0.0188)	0.0384*** (0.0029)	-0.1101*** (0.0030)	0.1917*** (0.0030)
<i>Sign comparison (Polymarket opening \rightarrow Kalshi):</i>					
		+ \rightarrow + \checkmark	- \rightarrow + \times	+ \rightarrow - \times	- \rightarrow + \times

Table 25: Distance between Polymarket and Kalshi slope coefficients at each timing point. $\Delta\beta_j = \hat{\beta}_j^{\text{PM}} - \hat{\beta}_j^{\text{Kalshi}}$ for each covariate j . Decreasing distances indicate convergence toward the Kalshi coefficient pattern.

Timing	Signed difference $\Delta\beta$			Distance		
	$\Delta\beta_{\text{vol}}$	$\Delta\beta_{\text{dur}}$	$\Delta\beta_{\text{ext}}$	L_1	L_2	Reduction
PM 5% (opening)	-0.1101	+0.2532	-0.6695	1.0328	0.7242	—
PM 20%	-0.1000	+0.2349	-0.5535	0.8883	0.6095	14%
PM 50% (mid-life)	-0.0925	+0.2151	-0.3824	0.6900	0.4484	33%
PM 80% (late-life)	-0.0851	+0.1662	-0.3997	0.6510	0.4411	37%

A.1 External Benchmark Details

This appendix provides methodological details for the external benchmark validation reported in Section 5.6.

Elo model specification. I build Elo ratings from the complete 2025–26 NBA regular season (1,135 games, 30 teams) using a standard recursive update. The parameters are $K = 28$ (update factor) and home-court advantage = 42 Elo points, calibrated to the modern NBA home-win rate of approximately 56%. All teams are initialized at Elo = 1500; preseason and All-Star games are excluded.

Elo calibration. The model achieves a Brier score of 0.218 on the 1,135-game sample. Binned calibration shows reasonable alignment between predicted and realized home-win rates, with the strongest calibration in the 30–80% predicted probability range.

Sportsbook validation. To validate the Elo model against a sharper external benchmark, I compare its predictions to consensus moneyline odds from The Odds API for 13 contemporaneous NBA games. The consensus probability is the mean across nine bookmakers, with overround removed by normalization. The correlation between Elo and sportsbook probabilities is $r = 0.618$, with MAE = 0.166 and RMSE = 0.200. The moderate correlation confirms that the Elo model captures a substantial share of the variation in sharp-market pricing, while the residual noise inflates the contract-level $\hat{\lambda}_i$ estimates relative to what a sportsbook-based benchmark would yield.

Matching procedure. I identify Polymarket NBA game contracts by regex matching on the title format “Team A vs. Team B”, requiring both team names to normalize to one of 30 canonical NBA team names via an alias table. Each contract is matched to the closest Elo game involving the same team pair within a $[-1, +5]$ -day window around the contract’s creation date. Of 80 contracts passing team normalization, 51 are successfully matched; the 29 unmatched contracts reference games outside the matching window or future unplayed games.

Contract-level $\hat{\lambda}_i$. For each matched contract, the Wang parameter is computed as $\hat{\lambda}_i = \Phi^{-1}(p_i^{\text{Polymarket}}) - \Phi^{-1}(\hat{p}_i^{\text{Elo}})$, where $p_i^{\text{Polymarket}}$ is the opening price (first-5% midpoint) and \hat{p}_i^{Elo} is the pre-game Elo probability assigned to the first-named team.

OLS regression. A cross-sectional regression of $\hat{\lambda}_i$ on $\ln(\text{Volume})$ and price extremity $|p_i - 0.5|$ finds neither covariate significant at conventional levels ($N = 51$; Table 16, Panel B), though the negative extremity coefficient ($\hat{\beta} = -0.72$, $p = 0.094$) is suggestive of pricing wedge concentrated near even-odds contracts. The limited power reflects the small matched sample.